

Zero PM

Zero pollution of Persistent, Mobile substances

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Summary

The document presents a series of three working papers that aim to stimulate and support policy changes to more effectively tackle persistent, mobile and toxic (PMT) substances and very persistent, very mobile (vPvM) substances. The three reports each aim to build on the Deliverable 3.1 of ZeroPM, which reviewed the EU's overarching policy ambitions, objectives, and targets for the sustainable use of chemicals. Further these reports are part of future work in to develop and disseminate policy options, road maps and policy briefs for PMT/vPvM substances. The first paper presents a summary of risk management option analysis (RMOA) of PMT/vPvM substances already assessed as substances of very high concern (SVHC) under the REACH regulation. The second presents an analysis of EU strategies related to PMT/vPvM substances, while the third report shows a case study on triazoles as potential PMT/vPvM substance group, exploring substance-specific regulatory approaches.

List of abbreviations

CLP	Regulation 1272/2008/EC on classification, labelling and packaging of substances and mixtures, amending and repealing Directives 67/548/EEC and 1999/45/EC, and amending Regulation (EC) No 1907/2006
B	Bioaccumulative
BAuA	Federal Institute for Occupational Safety and Health (Bundesanstalt für Arbeiterschutz und Arbeitsmedizin)
BAT	Best Available Technique
BREF	Best Available Technique Reference Document
CLH	Harmonised Classification and Labelling
CLP	Regulation 1272/2008/EC on classification, labelling and packaging of substances and mixtures, amending and repealing Directives 67/548/EEC and 1999/45/EC, and amending Regulation (EC) No 1907/2006
D _{ow}	Octanol-water distribution coefficient for all species
ECHA	European Chemicals Agency
EloC	Equivalent level of concern
log K_{oc}	Soil sorption coefficient normalized to the total organic carbon
M	Mobility criterion
P	Persistent criterion
PBT	Persistent, Bioaccumulative and Toxic
NOEC	No observed effect concentration
PMT	Persistent, mobile and toxic
REACH	Regulation (EC) No 1907/2006 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 18 December 2006 concerning the Registration, Evaluation, Authorisation and Restriction of Chemicals (REACH)
RMOA	Risk Management Option Analysis
STOT RE	Specific target organ toxicity - repeat exposure
SVHC	Substances that may have serious and often irreversible effects on human health and the environment can be identified as substances of very high concern (SVHCs) under the REACH regulation.
T	Toxic
UBA	German environment Agency (Umweltbundesamt)
vP	Very persistent
vM	Very mobile
vPvB	Very persistent and very bioaccumulative
vPvM	Very persistent and very mobile

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1 Background

ZeroPM, which stands for Zero pollution of Persistent, Mobile substances, is a 5 year long, European research project funded under the Horizon 2020 research and innovation program. ZeroPM will interlink and synergize three strategies to protect the environment and human health from persistent and mobile substances: Prevent, Prioritize and Remove. To do this, ZeroPM will develop an evidence-based multilevel framework. The framework will guide policy, technological and market incentives to minimize use, emissions and pollution of persistent and mobile substances.

The work package ‘Policy analysis, development, and assessment’ (Work Package 3) aims to contribute to the strengthening and enforcement of the EU chemicals policy framework in order to more effectively regulate persistent, mobile and toxic (PMT) and very persistent and very mobile (vPvM) substances as well as incentivise and create an enabling environment for the uptake of alternative, sustainable chemicals

2 Introduction and theoretical considerations

2.1 Introduction

This series of working papers is a comprehensive examination of regulatory gaps and opportunities of PMT (Persistent, Mobile, and Toxic) and vPvM (very Persistent and very Mobile) substances. It consists of three reports, each focusing on a distinct yet interconnected aspect of regulatory analysis. Before delving into the specific findings of the individual reports, a theoretical framework is presented to outline how the overarching document is conceptualized.

In a first step, reports 1 and 2 explore general methodologies for identifying regulatory gaps and opportunities. Both reports each focus on integrating a different distinct perspective representing key policy actors. Report 1 examines Risk Management Option Analysis (RMOA) proposals developed by national competent agencies for environmental protection. This analysis aims to highlight how past RMOAs of

PMT/vPvM substances, already classified as Substances of Very High Concern (SVHCs), can serve as learning examples for future regulatory processes. The report includes a detailed assessment of four substances: Melamine (EC 203-615-4), GenX (2,3,3,3-tetrafluoro-2-(heptafluoropropoxy)propionic acid) (EC 799-974-4), 1,4-Dioxane (204-661-8), and Perfluorobutane sulfonic acid (PFBS) (EC 799-977-0). Through this analysis, insights are gained into various regulatory mechanisms such as SVHC identification, harmonized classification and labelling, authorisation, and restriction measures and their significance as tools for the regulation of PMT/vPvM substances. Report 2 shifts focus to the perspective of the European Commission's policy framework, providing a thorough analysis of 13 EU strategies and action plans. The primary objective is to identify regulatory gaps and opportunities for PMT/vPvM substances by assessing the 124 actions outlined in these documents. Strategies under the European Green Deal, alongside pre-existing strategies, are examined to uncover areas where regulatory improvements are needed. Issues such as the circular economy, data availability, and the global dimension of chemicals management are considered. This report evaluates the aims, relevant legislation, targeted substance groups, and sectors mentioned in these strategic documents. Importantly, in its final section, it also synthesizes the key findings of Reports 1 and 2, drawing together insights.

In a second step, Report 3 narrows the focus to a case study on triazoles, offering a substance-specific investigation into regulatory gaps and opportunities of this PMT/vPvM substance. The report provides an overview of triazole chemistry, usage, and the regulatory approaches to grouping substances. It also considers the transformation products of triazoles, comparing their regulatory status across biocides, plant protection products, and pharmaceuticals. Through close collaboration with experts from various sections of the Umweltbundesamt (UBA; German Environment Agency), this report presents an understanding of the current legal framework surrounding triazole regulation, highlighting potential pathways for regulatory advancements.

Together, the three reports form a cohesive analysis of the regulatory gaps and opportunities that emerge for PMT/vPvM substances, presenting both broad and specific

approaches and corresponding insights. Results gained here aim to inform future policy development of policy options for PMT/vPvM substances within ZeroPM task 3.3.

2.2 Theoretical considerations

2.2.1 Identification of generic regulatory gaps and opportunities

What are regulatory gaps and their corresponding opportunities and how can they be identified? To answer the first part of this question, the following definition is used: “[Regulatory] gaps in a given legal framework are generally situations in which a desired (legal) state does not exist or in which objectives are difficult to realize, or not realised yet. In such situations, different actors identify different gaps or specific considerations. Such specific considerations can be, for example, environmental protection by preventing the entry of harmful substances into the environment, the generation of economic profits or the maximization of electoral votes” (Mohr et al. 2024). In addition, regulatory opportunities emerge from regulatory gaps. Conversely, existing regulatory opportunities can inform existing regulatory gaps. As for how to identify those gaps and opportunities for PMT/vPvM substances, this can be achieved by integrating different perspectives of various policy related actors. For this, report 1 focuses on an examination of Risk Management Option Analysis (RMOA) proposals by national competent agencies for environmental protection. Report 2 concentrates on an analysis of action plans and strategy documents from the European Commission.

2.2.2 The new hazard classes PMT and vPvM under CLP

To understand regulatory gaps and opportunities that might emerge, it is necessary to consider regulatory measures already in place to protect the environment and human health from PMT and vPvM substances. For this, first it is important to note that the regulation of PMT and vPvM substances without being coupled with other substance properties like bioaccumulation (B), represents a new approach. This approach goes back to the German Environment Agencies (Umweltbundesamt - UBA) first idea to close the regulatory gap between the REACH regulation (Registration, Evaluation, Authorisation and Restriction of Chemicals) and the protection of drinking water resources in 2009 and the subsequent development and introduction of criteria covering

PMT and vPvM substances (Hale et al. 2020; Klein & Neumann 2009; Neumann 2012; Neumann & Dieter (2014); Neumann et al. 2015; Neumann & Schliebner 2019).

Hereinafter activities initiated by the European Commission resulted in the implementation of new hazard classes under the CLP (classification, labelling and packaging) regulation. The classification criteria can be seen in appendix A. The hazard classes PMT and vPvM entered into force on the 20th April of 2023 (European Commission 2022). Under these hazard classes substances must be evaluated for persistence, mobility, and toxicity to determine their potential hazards to human health and the environment, applicable to both new and existing substances not previously assessed. Companies are required to conduct self-classification before market entry, ensuring compliance with new regulations aimed at identifying chemicals that pose risks to drinking water resources and environmental safety.

The introduction of the new hazard classes under CLP causes knock-on effects that affect EU legal acts that contain obligations triggered by the CLP hazard classification and/or hazardous properties. Acts that contain obligations applicable to hazardous substances as defined in Article 3 of the CLP Regulation automatically cover the new hazard classes. This is, for example, the case for the Industrial Emission Directive, which refers to the definition of hazardous substances under CLP (Article 3(18) of the IED) and defines several obligations for hazardous substances regarding permit conditions, the setting up of an environmental management system and site closure¹. Other acts using specific hazard classes for triggering generic prohibitions or other obligations (e.g. BPR, PPPR, Toys Regulation, Cosmetics Regulation) but that do not yet refer to the new hazard classes may be expected to be revised (or are currently being revised). Similarly, acts referring to properties of concern that were previously not included under Article 3 of the CLP Regulation (PBT, vPvB, endocrine disruption) may be expected to be revised to refer to CLP hazard classification. In the wake of the Green Deal, many EU acts have

¹ Permit conditions must include appropriate requirements for the monitoring of relevant hazardous substances likely to be found on site in soil, surface and groundwater (Article 14(1)(e)); the environmental management system (EMS), which should be established by all operators of installations falling in the scope of the Directive, must include measures to prevent or reduce the use or emissions of hazardous substances, and a chemicals inventory of the hazardous substances present in or emitted from the installation, including a risk assessment of the impact of such substances on human health and the environment, as well as an analysis of the possibilities to substitute them with safer alternatives or reduce their use or emissions (Article 14a); Rules on site closure state the operator must assess the state of soil and groundwater contamination by relevant hazardous substances and if the installation has caused significant pollution, take measure to return the site to its initial state (Article 22).

been revised and some new legislation now includes obligations based on hazard classification such as the Ecodesign for Sustainable Products Regulation, which includes all new hazard classes in the definition of 'substance of concern' and provides that performance requirements restricting the use of substances of concern during the manufacturing process of a product and/or the presence of such substances in the final product can be adopted if these substances impede the reuse or recycling of the product.

The Chemicals Strategy for Sustainability towards a Toxic Free Environment (CSS) announced "to amend REACH Article 57 to add endocrine disruptors, persistent, mobile and toxic (PMT) and very persistent and very mobile (vPvM) substances to the list of substances of very high concern" by 2022 (COM(2020) 667 final). This amendment has been delayed and would have significant legal consequences for a multitude of areas of chemical regulation in a similar fashion compared to and especially in combination with the new hazard classes under CLP. This is highlighted as currently PMT and vPvM substances can be identified as SVHCs and regulated accordingly only via case-by-case decisions under Article 57 (f) of REACH (Regulation (EC) No 1907/2006). Article 57 (f) allows the inclusion of a substance in the corresponding list of SVHCs if scientific evidence can be presented on effects, that demonstrate serious harm to human health or the environment, in the form of an "equivalent level of concern" (EloC) as a substance meeting the Annex XIII criteria for PBT/vPvB (Bakker et al. 2017; Hale et al. 2020).

"In theory, REACH Article 57(f) might be invoked if evidence can be presented that a vP substance gives rise to an equivalent level of concern as a substance meeting the criteria for PBT/vPvB. But such an approach would also mean an ad hoc, case-by-case approach, which would not be sufficient to address e.g. the 3000+ extremely persistent highly fluorinated substances on the market today" (Bakker et al. 2017: 11).

However, due to the complex procedure, until now only a handful of selected PMT and/or vPvM substances were included to the candidate list so far via Article 57 (f) of REACH. Therefore, the process can be designated as a cumbersome detour in terms of regulatory efficiency and as a regulatory gap on its own.

3 Report 1: RMOA analysis of PMT/vPvM substances already assessed as SVHC

3.1 Research Approach

One of the largest problems when assessing remaining regulatory gaps and opportunities for PMT/vPvM substances is related to the fact that only a handful of PMT/vPvM substances have been regulated. Owing to this, it is hard to identify legal patterns for PMT/vPvM substances, which leaves a conundrum. How does one find legal gaps and or opportunities in the European legal framework in a systematic way? To approach this question, report 1 incorporates the perspectives of national competent agencies and refers to RMOAs for substances with PMT/vPvM properties. For this purpose, RMOA conclusion documents open for the public are used as a data source. By looking at the Candidate list provided by ECHA (European Chemicals Agency), which lists substances of very high concern (SVHC) and which offers the option to filter listed substances for their reason of inclusion to the Candidate list, the following PMT/vPvM substances are identified to be of interest for the analysis of this report:

- Melamine
- 2,3,3,3-tetrafluoro-2-(heptafluoropropoxy)propionic acid, its salts and its acyl halides (GenX)
- 1,4-Dioxane
- Perfluorobutane sulfonic acid (PFBS) and its salts

The applied filter to look for PMT/vPvM substances used on ECHAs Candidate list is “reason of inclusion: “equivalent level of concern having probable serious effects to the environment (article 57 (f) – environment)” (ECHA 2023b).

The four PMT/vPvM substances listed above were included in the candidate list before the hazard classes PMT and vPvM were introduced under CLP. The four substances are selected as cases for analysis for two reasons. First, cases of already regulated PMT/vPvM substances can serve as precedents for future regulatory considerations and therefore as learning examples for the identification of regulatory gaps and opportunities. Regulation is based on REACH article 57 (f), that states an equivalent level of concern (EloC) compared to other criteria laid down in article 57 (a-e) that effects the environment by having probable serious effects (ECHA 2023b; Regulation

(EC) No 1907/2006). For each of the four substances, prior to their identification as SVHC, a corresponding RMOA was published. Second, all four substances are PMT/vPvM substances and share similar environmental concerns. Their Physiochemical properties are listed in Table 1.

Table 1: Physiochemical properties of the four selected cases of PMT/vPvM substances

Cas No.	EC No.	Name	Other REACH substances & precursors	EC PMT/vPvM conclusion	P rationale	M rationale	T rationale
108-78-1	203-615-4	Melamine	(p)203-615-4; (s1)236-860-0; (s1)239-590-1; (s1)253-575-7; (s1)255-449-7; (s1)403-290-0; (s2)605-959-4; (s2)939-379-0	vPvM & PMT	vP: No degradation in a OECD TG 309 (Hofman-Caris and Claßen, 2020). Calculated half-life melamine in water: >10.000 days; measured max t1/2.max(d) in soil = 913 days (eChemPortal database)	vM exp log Koc=1.1	Carc. 2, STOTE RE 2, under assessment as Endocrine Disrupting
123-91-1	204-661-8	1,4-dioxane	(p)204-661-8; (s2)944-082-4	vPvM & PMT	vP: No degradation in a OECD TG 309 (Hofman-Caris and Claßen, 2020), calculated half-life 1,4-dioxane: >10.000 days. No significant biodegradation in 301F test.	vM min Dow=-0.4 (2a)	Carc1B
62037-80-3	700-242-3	GenX		vPvM & PMT	vP: short-chain PFAS, degradation is negligble under ambient circumstances	vM exp log Koc=1.1	STOTE RE 2
375-73-5	206-793-1	PFBS	(s1)249-616-3; (s1)444-440-5; (s1)452-310-4; (s2)432-660-4; (s2)468-770-4; (s2)477-300-7; (s2)478-340-8; (p)206-793-1	vPvM & PMT	vP: short-chain PFAS, degradation is negligble under ambient circumstances	vM exp log Koc=1.4	Ecotoxic

Taken from Arp et al. (2023).

RMOAs are voluntary evaluations and opinions on selected substances by EU member state competent authorities (e.g. environmental agencies) or ECHA (by request of the European Commission). Their purpose is to promote early discussion, sharing information and to help authorities decide, if regulatory risk management measures are necessary, and if so, which of these measures are suitable. For this, available information is compiled from REACH and CLP, but also from other relevant sources as well. It should be noted, that RMOAs can be based on varying levels of information, which can include evidence of practical workability of deduced regulatory measures like authorisation or restriction processes, technical possibilities, existence of alternative substances and or socio-economic data. RMOAs are not part of the actual legal process of EU chemicals legislation like REACH or CLP and therefore have no direct legal impact, since conclusions represent only the views of the authorities that prepared the RMOA (BAuA 2022; COM(2018) 116 final; ECHA 2023a).

RMOAs are used here to identify regulatory gaps and opportunities as the four substances were already identified as SVHC before their respective RMOAs were published. Therefore, legal action did take place for those substances and the corresponding RMOAs entail valid (in part already successful) proposals for regulatory measures (including proposals for SVHC identification). Therefore, those RMOAs can be reasonably viewed as successful examples of valid legal recommendations and might function as a potential basis for future regulation of other PMT/vPvM substances. Since RMOAs reflect an agency perspective that includes administrative and regulatory considerations, taken together this means that RMOAs constitute a form of voluntary input into the policy-making processes of European chemicals legislation. They represent insights and recommendations of experts that are published before the actual legal decisions took place on a case-by-case basis and can therefore cast light on legal gaps and opportunities of the time of their writing.

In the following, the proposals for regulatory measures of the RMOAs for the four selected substances with regard to their PMT/vPvM properties are compared. Following this, differences and similarities are identified which are used to provide an idea of a

general direction future regulation may adopt to handle concerns stemming from PMT/vPvM substances not yet regulated.

3.2 Results

3.2.1 SVHC identification

Appendix B discusses the content of the four analysed RMOAs in detail, while table 2 lists the proposed measures of the RMOAs. Both address SVHC identification. Table 2 shows information about formal proposals collected from the conclusion tick boxes found in the respective RMOAs and includes selected unofficial, informal recommendations found in the RMOA, that did not make it into the RMOA conclusion tick boxes. Those recommendations refer to measures the authors of the RMOA are generally in favour of, but are deemed as not practicable due to factors like e.g. time or data restraints or other regulatory processes that should be preferred at the time of publishing the RMOA.

Table 2: Summary of proposed RMOA measures

Substance	RMOA proposals					
	Harmonised classification and labelling	Identification as SVHC	Authorisation under REACH	Restriction under REACH	Other Measures EU-wide	Not EU-wide
PFBS		X		X		X
GenX	X	X		X		X
Melamine	X	X			X	
1,4-Dioxane		X		X	X	

Unofficial, informal recommendations found in the RMOA are highlighted in blue.

All four RMOAs support the identification of the analyzed substances as SVHC as a first regulatory measure. Given that this was the route followed, this is not surprising. SVHC identification is consistently highlighted as the first step for further legal engagement and follow-up regulation and requires an EU-wide unanimous agreement that the substance properties do cause a hazard for human health or the environment. It incorporates the precautionary principle. Follow-up actions include not only potential attempts for authorization and restriction under REACH, but can also involve other downstream legislation. In addition, SVHC identification might help indirectly by

triggering national chemicals legislation and supports via a formal recognition of concerns, that can serve as an early warning system, offers an incentive for substitution efforts and opens up information pathways for consumers and downstream users. When identifying SVHC it is important to consider whether related substances to the substance in question should be identified. For example, in the case of HFPO-DA (trade name GenX), its salts, FRD-902, FRD-903 and its potassium salt were also identified as SVHCs. The SVHC identifications for the four analyzed cases are based on article 57 (f) of REACH and therefore on ELoC. However, the new hazard classes PMT, EUH450 (can cause long-lasting and diffuse contamination of water resources) and vPvM, EUH451 (can cause very long-lasting and diffuse contamination of water resources) that are now under the CLP regulation provide new (legal) possibilities for dealing with PMT/vPvM substances. At least in terms of hazard class, persistence coupled with mobility now stands on its own, without having to reference to an equivalent level of concern. It remains to be seen, if the announced revision of REACH continues this undertaking and includes PMT and vPvM into article 57 as well. If so, this would act as a potential game changer for PMT/vPvM substances and enable direct regulation without going the path of a complicated workaround like ELoC under article 57 (f) of REACH (European Commission 2023c; Regulation (EC) No 1272/2008; Regulation (EC) No 1907/2006).

3.2.2 Authorisation

Authorisation translates to an inclusion of the substances in question into annex XIV of REACH, which means that “*Companies that want to continue using a substance included in the Authorisation List after the sunset date need to prepare an application for authorisation, submit it before the latest application date and have a positive authorisation decision by the European Commission*” (ECHA 2023d). None of the analysed RMOAs concluded that the inclusion of their respective substance into annex XIV of REACH and corresponding authorisation regimes was a preferred regulatory measure. The RMOAs highlight concerns regarding the effectiveness of actually reducing overall emissions compared to merely shifting production from EU countries into non-EU countries. The RMOAs of PFBS, GenX and 1,4-Dioxane highlight the

limitations of authorisation in terms of imported articles. The import of articles is not covered by authorisation, therefore production and use outside of Europe will be not affected for the most part. This includes unintended low occurrences in mixtures and other substances (e.g. impurities), as is the case for 1,4-Dioxane. It is also of note that the RMOA for 1,4-Dioxane suggests that authorisation efforts might even hinder future restriction approaches, if used imprudently. Though from a point of practicability and implementation, for substances with an estimated relatively low number of industrial users like GenX, authorisation might still be considered, as it offers an advantage in terms of bureaucratic processing. This can be considered less of a general regulatory opportunity per se and more of a condition for the existence of such an opportunity in certain cases.

3.2.3 Restriction

In contrast to authorization, inclusion of a substance into annex XVII of REACH in the form of a restriction, that limits or bans manufacture, use and the placing on the market is suggested by the RMOA for PFBS and 1,4-Dioxane. In addition, although the RMOA for GenX does not formally recommend a restriction because of insufficient data, it strongly emphasizes the potential need for restriction after further evaluation. Because of this, for the purpose of identifying potential gaps and opportunities, the GenX-RMOA is considered of supporting restriction as a regulatory measure as well and is therefore marked in Table 1 under restriction accordingly. In terms of regulatory advantages that restrictions might be able to offer for regulating PMT/vPvM substances, all three RMOAs highlight the possibility to address not only EU-wide articles, but also articles from outside the EU. With that, emissions originating from articles that contain (e.g. residual amounts of) substances of concern can be regulated as well. In addition, restrictions may allow groups of substances to be addressed as well as offering the possibility of targeted risk management by introducing restrictions that are custom-fit for specified uses. Setting emission limits or restricting maximum allowed (residual) concentrations are examples of this.

While authorization might be a suitable regulatory measure for substances with a comparably low number of registrants, the opposite is true for restriction. Substances with a high production and use tonnage and a corresponding high number of registrants that would require many applications if it were for authorisation, can be better managed by authorities in cases where restriction applies. The restriction process encompasses a complex procedure which requires sufficient data and time. For substances that need to be regulated as soon as possible, other regulatory measures may be preferred. Those were the reasons cited against a restriction in the RMOA for Melamine.

3.2.4 Harmonised classification and labelling

Harmonised classification and labelling under the CLP regulation was only proposed for Melamine to address reproductive toxicity via Repr. 2, H361f. The RMOA for GenX does favor harmonised classification and labelling, but no hazard criteria for protecting human health and the environment was listed in the respective conclusion tick box of the RMOA at the time. Main reason for this was a lack of data. Given the new hazard classes PMT and vPvM under CLP, there may be an upward trend in the number of RMOAs recommending this route. Harmonized classification and labelling constitutes a window of opportunity that should be encouraged to be used in the process of future regulation of PMT/vPvM substances.

3.2.5 Other measures

Regarding other EU-wide regulatory measures, both RMOAs of Melamine and 1,4-Dioxane proposed occupational exposure limits for the workplace by resorting to IOELVs or BOELVs. It was also suggested that registration dossiers be updated by registrants for 1,4-Dioxane. This measure could be easily applied for other PMT/vPvM substances as well. Most other EU-wide regulatory measures were discarded as inappropriate by the respective RMOAs though. This is due to time and data restraints for the most part. This holds true for most evaluated international, not-EU-wide, measures as well, that are covered by the RMOAs. Only worldwide regulation by the Stockholm Convention was considered effective by the RMOA for PFBS. Again, it should be mentioned that for the most part, this is due to the time-consuming process,

the need for decisive and fast regulatory action as well as lingering uncertainties regarding the substances in question. Because of this, regulatory measures under the Stockholm Convention in parallel to EU-wide regulatory action are considered as a complementary option according to the RMOA covering GenX. Because of this, GenX is marked for an unofficial, informal recommendation for not EU-wide measures in Table 2.

3.2.6 Summary of results

Given that only a limited amount of PMT/vPvM substances are classified as SVHC for their PMT/vPvM properties at the time being, only four RMOAs were analysed and results must be considered with slight caution. In addition, the RMOAs cover the perspective of agencies and therefore of state actors only. Despite this, lessons can be learned from those few substances that have shown that regulatory measures for PMT/vPvM substances are possible. Based on the above the following can be summarized and core findings of this chapter are depicted in Table 3:

1. As a first step, SVHC identification appears to be the most important tool for unregulated PMT/vPvM substances. It draws attention to the subject and helps pave the way for further legal activities. SVHC identification may also be supported by the newly introduced PMT/vPvM hazard classes under CLP. Together, this constitutes one of the biggest opportunities for regulating PMT/vPvM substances in the future. To harness this opportunity, it is crucial the REACH revision continues the path set up by CLP and goes ahead as announced in the CSS in regards to PMT and vPvM substances (COM(2020) 667 final). Though at the time of writing, the revision was delayed, thus providing a regulatory gaps.
2. Restriction is preferred over authorisation as a regulatory measure for PMT/vPvM substances so far. However, tonnage, number of registrants and the location of the production site are important to consider when selecting the most appropriate regulatory measure. This is related to potential shifts of production from EU into non-EU countries for imported articles as well as bureaucratic manageability. Whilst

restrictions can be time-consuming tasks, they are able to include whole substance groups rather than being limited to individual substances. Owing to this, for big groups of substances, the time investments can pay off and a restriction can pose a regulatory opportunity under the right circumstances. Consequently, multiple RMOAs are in favour of restrictions if time and or data constraints leave enough room for this kind of regulatory action. A recent example of this is the broad PFAS restriction where the PFAS class is targeted for restriction (ECHA 2023j). It seems feasible that future restrictions may follow this path and target other PMT/vPvM substance groups. One such possibility could be the case of Triazoles that will be further explored in the following report of this series of working papers.

3. Agencies responsible for writing RMOAs concentrate on regulation under REACH and CLP for PMT/vPvM substances. Other regulatory measures are evaluated in the analysed RMOAs, but these are often complementary in nature or not considered adequate from an agency perspective. Out of these measures, inclusion of PMT/vPvM substances into the Stockholm Convention is contemplated the most. Both, the cases of GenX and PFBS show this. However, reservations due to time and data constraints limit recommendations. Given that emissions of PMT/vPvM substances do not stop at national borders, an international perspective is needed, which constitutes another regulatory gap. Alternatives like voluntary industry action are not addressed as well in the RMOAs.
4. Time and data restraints constitute one of the biggest factors in selecting the most appropriate regulatory options for PMT/vPvM substances. This is especially true for substances with potentially irreversible effects, rising emissions and or that steadily increase with time in the environment. Under these conditions, regulatory decision making is urged to act. For example the case of GenX: *“Because of the expected time to results and the already very high concern for FRD-902 based on the information described in this RMOA, of which an important factor is its current widespread environmental appearance in the Netherlands and elsewhere in Europe that developed over a period of only 5 – 6 years (2012 – 2018), it is concluded not to await any information coming from the ongoing SEv but to initiate regulatory*

measures as soon as possible“ (RIVM 2018: 7). This might lead to short time regulatory action and gaps in long time regulatory measures. More complex regulatory processes such as restrictions or inclusions in the Stockholm Convention may not be pursued further because of this. Therefore, a potential regulatory opportunity is to purposely pursue long term measures in parallel with short term action. Consequently, all measures that speed up processes like an introduction of PMT/vPvM criteria under REACH article 57, which would enable to regulate PMT/vPvM substances without going a detour by using ELoC under article 57 (f) can be considered as regulatory opportunities.

- ▼ Data gaps result in regulatory gaps. The RMOA of 1,4-Dioxane reflected that emissions of polyethyleneterephthalate and from polyester fibre manufacturing caused emissions of 1,4-Dioxane. However, the significance of these findings is unclear. Polymers are exempt for obligations according to title II of REACH (registration) and title VI of REACH (Evaluation). ECHA (2023k) notes, that “A polymer, as any other substance defined in Article 3(1), can also contain additives necessary to preserve the stability of the polymer and impurities deriving from the manufacturing process. These stabilisers and impurities are considered to be part of the substance and do not have to be registered separately.” From this follows that no information on polymers is available, e.g. on production volumes and impurities. Hence, the evaluation of regulatory needs for polymers and their impurities, need to rely on different data sources than those from the REACH registration database. This creates an extra burden in the regulatory process and therefore can be considered as another regulatory gap.

Table 3: Summary of gaps and opportunities drawn from RMOA comparison

Summary of results	
Gaps	Opportunities
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Delay of amending REACH Article 57 to add PMT and vPvM substances to the list of substances of very high concern • Data and time constraints can lead to primarily short term regulatory action and gaps in long term regulatory measures • Regulatory processes/advancements are slow in the international context (e.g. Stockholm Convention) • Emissions do not stop at national borders. • Authorization is lacking in terms of efficient implementation based on gaps in relation to the import of products 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • CLH by means of the new PMT/vPvM hazard classes under CLP and their legal consequences • SVHC identification as a legal gateway into subsequent regulation • Restrictions in the absence of data and time constraints • REACH and CLP offer the greatest potential for regulation

3.3 Report 1 conclusion

Report 1 identified potential regulatory gaps and opportunities for PMT/vPvM substances, which can be used for subsequent substance-specific research of the European legal framework for chemicals and the development of suitable policy options. The analysis of RMOAs for already regulated PMT/vPvM substances as a guide for first steps of possible future regulation allowed legal gaps as well as opportunities to be identified for those PMT/vPvM substances that are not regulated yet. Core findings highlight the significance of SVHC identification and in extension of the new PMT and vPvM hazard classes under CLP and the importance of the forthcoming REACH revision. This is especially true, since regulatory measures outside of REACH and CLP seem to play more of a complementary role from an agency perspective. Thus, the delay of the REACH revision to article 57 to add PMT/vPvM substances to the list of SVHC can be identified as a regulatory gap. Restriction under REACH plays an important role as a regulatory measure as well, though it is subjected to time and data restraints as a deciding factor in terms of appropriateness.

4 Report 2: Analysis of EU strategies and action plans

4.1 Research Approach

Report 2 approaches the identification of regulatory gaps and opportunities in the European chemicals policy framework by focusing on the perspective of the European Commission. For this purpose, EU strategies and action plans adopted under the European Green Deal and some additional strategies adopted prior to the European Green Deal are examined (COM(2019) 640 final). Among the subjects contained in these strategies and action plans, are issues related to e.g. the circular economy, the global dimension, data availability or ambitions to amend specific regulations or directives. Announced actions contained within the corresponding appendices of these strategies and action plans represent areas which the EU acknowledges a need for attention and sees a necessity to make changes. This unlocks potential for policy change. Therefore, the intersections of those actions (and therefore areas given attention) with the current regulation of PMT/vPvM substances show where regulatory opportunities and regulatory gaps, can be located.

Figure 1: Intersection of current regulation of PMT/vPvM substances and announced actions of EU strategies and action plans

The different aspects EU strategies are aimed towards can be described as categories. Such categories can be e.g. the general aims of the strategy, relevant legislation concerned with the matter of the strategy or specific substances addressed by the strategy. Those categories are identified via desk research by a) preliminary theoretical

consideration and b) in an inductive way by means of extraction from the strategies and action plans themselves. To each identified category multiple keywords are assigned, based on the content of the respective actions announced in the EU strategies and action plans. The total frequencies of the appearances of those keywords within all announced actions of the various EU strategies and action plans show areas of regulatory opportunities and gaps. Figure 2 visualizes this approach.

Figure 2: Locating regulatory gaps & opportunities via EU strategies/action plans

As described above, the following categories are identified:

- Aims
- Legislation
- Substance groups/substances
- Use
- Sectors/industrial branches
- General scope

“Aims” covers environmental keywords like environmental media (air, water, etc.) and social keywords (human health, consumers, etc.). “Legislation” relates to directives, regulations or other legal documents that will be affected by actions announced in the corresponding strategy documents. “Substance groups/substances” covers explicitly stated substances or groups of substances like PFAS, but also broader defined keywords such as endocrine disruptors. Regarding “use” and “sectors/industrial branches”, a table is used, that loosely follows the nomenclature proposed by Glüge et al. (2020), which covers “Industry branches”. This nomenclature was originally intended for PFAS. Since

a lot of PFAS are PMT/vPvM substances, the approach proves to be sufficient for the purpose of this analysis as well. To better mirror the contents of the EU strategies and action plans, the keywords “*childcare articles & toys*”, “*food additives*” and “*food contact materials*” are added to “use”. For “sectors/industrial branches” “*cosmetics*” is added. Finally, the category “*General scope*” covers all noteworthy areas, EU actions are aiming at, that do not fit into the other categories and that typically encompass broad concepts like circular economy or international action.

Frequencies are assigned to the keywords in the following way: A) For the categories of “use”, “sectors/industrial branches” and “general scope”, announced actions in EU strategy documents and action plans are counted under a keyword if their relevant characteristics can be logically inferred from the text of the strategy document or action plan. B) For the categories of “legislation”, “substances” or “aims”, announced actions in EU strategy documents and action plans are counted under a keyword if the keyword is explicitly mentioned in the text of the strategy document or action plan. Since many of the actions described are somewhat vague and open to interpretation, inclusion by explicit mention is deemed the preferred way of analysis. Using this method may lead to some keywords in actions being overlooked – and thus some regulatory gaps and opportunities – but the method ensures that the most prominent gaps and opportunities related to specific areas of interest are identified. It is plausible that these are the most promising for developing future policy options. Appendix C lists all 124 analyzed action of the selected EU strategies and action plans that are deemed of relevance for PMT/vPvM substances according to the results of ZeroPM deliverable 3.1. An overview of all categories, keywords and frequencies can also be found in appendix C. The determined frequencies for each keyword that relates to a respective category is shown in table 4 - 9.

Case selection of EU strategy papers, action plans and actions are based on the findings of ZeroPMs deliverable 3.1 and its corresponding templates for information gathering on strategic papers from appendixes B to N (Oulès 2022). Via these templates, a multitude of strategies and action plans were scanned for content, objectives and actions, to identify those relevant for PMT/vPvM substances. Based on these results, the

following strategies and action plans are used below for identifying regulatory gaps and or opportunities:

- EU Biodiversity Strategy
- Chemicals Strategy for Sustainability
- Circular Economy Action Plan
- EU Beating Cancer Plan
- Farm to Fork Strategy
- New Industrial Strategy for Europe
- Pharmaceutical Strategy for Europe
- Renovation Wave
- EU Soil Strategy for 2030
- Sustainable Blue Economy Strategy
- Sustainable Textile Strategy
- Strategy for Plastics in a circular Economy
- Zero Pollution Action Plan.

4.2 Results

4.2.1 Category: Aims

12 keywords were recorded in total – 8 representing environmental aims and 4 representing social aims, as presented in table 4. Out of these 12 keywords the most frequently occurring are waste (30), soil (24), water (23), human health (15) and biodiversity (10). Since one of the strategy papers is the EU Soil Strategy for 2030 and two of the strategies are related to the circular economy, these numbers are expected. This result shows the potential for policy change and points towards opportunities for PMT/vPvM substance regulation related to waste, soil and water policies as they are the current focal points of EU environmental engagement.

Table 4: Category of aims and corresponding frequencies of keywords within analyzed EU action plans and strategies

Aims	
Environmental categories:	Frequency
Waste	30
Soil	24
Water	23
Human health	15
Biodiversity	10
Climate	8
Marine	6
Air	2
Social categories:	Frequency
Consumers	7
Vulnerable groups	3
Workers	4
Children	1

4.2.2 Category: Legislation

As for the second category legislation, a total of 55 different keywords are counted. 9 of these keywords (marked in blue in Table 5) do not belong to legislation in the sense of directives or regulations but to EU initiatives, guidelines, announced future strategies or action plans not yet released (at the time of writing ZeroPM deliverable 3.1) or otherwise announced projects of EU initiative announced in the actions. Each keyword stands for a legislation referred to in one or more actions across the action plans and strategies. Table 6 shows the frequencies for these references. Out of 101 entries, 42 of those entries were accounted for only once. In consequence, the first 13 keywords combine half of all entries. The most frequently recorded legislations are REACH (13), the Industrial Emissions Directive (10) and the Ecodesign Directive (7). After that follows the Marine Strategy Framework Directive (4), the Ecolabel Regulation (4), the Sewage Sludge Directive (4), the Sustainable Use of Pesticides Directive (3), CLP (3) and the Environmental Quality Standards Directive (3). With that, REACH and CLP (to a lesser degree), as the two pillars of European chemical legislation, together with the Industrial Emissions Directive account for about a quarter of all relevant legislation referred to in the strategy documents. Overall these three legislations can be assumed to constitute the biggest opportunities for regulatory measures regarding PMT/vPvM substances, while the rest of European legislation plays a much smaller and somewhat divided role in terms of Commission attention. It is noteworthy, that the Cosmetics Regulation had only one

occurrence in the strategy documents despite PMT/vPvM substances are found in about 6.4% of cosmetic products available in the European market (Van Dijk et al. 2023).

Table 5: Category of legislation and corresponding frequencies of keywords within analyzed EU action plans and strategies

Legislation					
Title	Frequency	Title	Frequency	Title	Frequency
REACH	13	General Product Safety Directive	1	Regulation on the EU Ecolabel	1
Industrial Emissions Directive	10	Food additives Commission Regulation	1	Commission Initiative to address the unintentional release of microplastic into the environment	1
Ecodesign Directive	7	Stockholm Convention	1	Urban Waste Water Treatment Directive	1
Marine Strategy Framework Directive	4	Directive on end-of-life vehicles	1	Best Available Techniques (BAT) Reference Document (BREF)	1
Ecolabel Regulation	4	Directive on packaging and packaging waste	1	Waste Framework Directive	1
Sewage Sludge Directive	4	Drinking Water Directive	1	Upcoming EU waste legislation in 2024	1
Sustainable Use of Pesticides Directive	3	EU strategy for textiles	1	Regulation on Taxonomy for Sustainable Investments	1
CLP	3	Regulation on shipment of waste	1	Product legislation	1
Environmental Quality Standards Directive	3	EU Taxonomy Regulation	1	Directive on port reception facilities for the delivery of waste from ships	1
Ground Water Directive	2	Guidelines on State aid for climate, environmental protection and energy	1	Best Available Techniques reference document for aquaculture installations	1
European Pollutant Release and Transfer Register (E-PRTR)	2	European Plastic Strategy	1	Packaging and Packaging Waste Directive	1
Basel Convention	2	Circular Economy Monitoring Framework	1	Atlas of Demography	1
Sustainable Product Policy Initiative	2	Carcinogens and Mutagens Directive	1	Cancer Inequalities Registry	1
Directive on the restriction of the use of certain hazardous substances in electrical and electronic equipment	1	Occupational Safety and Health Strategic Framework 2021-2027	1	Bathing Water Directive	1
ECHA founding regulation	1	Batteries Regulation	1	European Climate Pact	1
Public Activities Coordination Tool	1	Directive on the Community code relating to medicinal products for human use	1		
Cosmetics Regulation	1	Regulation laying down Union procedures for the authorization and supervision of medicinal products for human use and establishing a European Medicines Agency	1		
Detergents Regulation	1	Soil Health Law (Commission adoption July-October 2023)	1		
Food Contact Materials Regulation	1	Directive as regards empowering consumers for the green transition through better protection against unfair practices and better information	1		
Toy Safety Directive	1	Textile Labelling Regulation	1		

4.2.3 Category: Substance groups/substances

Table 6 shows substance groups/substances. Out of the 23 keywords registered in total, only two were of significance for PMT/vPvM substances – PFAS with 6 occurrences and PMT/vPvM substances themselves, with just 2 occurrences. The substance group that occurred the most was endocrine disruptors with 11 occurrences. Given the huge EU focus on PFAS currently, this substance group may pave the way and provide another opportunity for the regulation of many PMT/vPvM substances. The upcoming PFAS broad restriction supports this assumption (ECHA 2023j). It is important to note, that the low number of occurrences of PMT/vPvM substances as a keyword indicates that those substances are only implicitly covered in terms of EU attention and it can be expected that most legal processes will occur via indirect regulation. Indirect in this sense refers to actions that do not explicitly target PMT/vPvM substances, but that cover those substances among other substances in addition. In a direct way, regulation of PMT/vPvM substances is called for in the CSS in the form of two actions that explicitly announce the intention to include PMT/vPvM substances to the list of substances of very high concern (SVHC) in REACH Article 57 and to add new hazard classes for PMT/vPvM substances under CLP and apply those across all legislation (COM(2020) 667 final).

Table 6: Category of substance groups/substances and corresponding frequencies of keywords within analyzed EU action plans and strategies

Substance groups/substances:					
Endocrine disruptors	11	Phosphorus	2	Benzene	1
CMRs	6	SVHC	1	Nickel compounds	1
PFAS	6	Polymers	2	Ammonia	1
PBT/vPvB	6	PMT/vPvM	2	Nitrate	1
Immunotoxicants & Neurotoxicants	4	Mixtures	1	Mercury	1
Substances toxic to specific organs	4	Carcinogenic substances	3	POP	1
Respiratory Sensitisers	3	Asbestos	1	Lead	1
Nitrogen	2	Acrylonitrile	1		

4.2.4 Category: Use

Table 7 shows the category of use. A total of 16 different keywords were recognized within the analyzed actions of EU action plans and strategies. Textile and upholstery (26) was seen most often. Paper & packaging (18), plastic rubber and resins (17), soil

remediation (15), water and effluent treatment (11) and electronic devices (10) follow in that order of frequency and all of these uses might offer regulatory opportunities for PMT/vPvM substances. These first 6 of the 16 keywords represent 97 out of 139 entries within the respective actions of the strategy documents and action plans. It should be noted that textile and upholstery, as well as soil remediation are represented by their own EU strategy document the Sustainable Textile Strategy and the EU Soil Strategy for 2030, respectively. There may also be some overlap for the use categories food contact materials and paper and packaging. Personal care products, which represent Cosmetic products as well, are underrepresented in the focus of EU strategies once more. The same is true for Pesticides and Pharmaceuticals. All three use cases are known for containing PMT/vPvM substances (Mohr et al. 2024).

Table 7: Category of use and corresponding frequencies of keywords within analyzed EU action plans and strategies

Use			
Textile and upholstery	26	Stone, concrete and tile	6
Paper and packaging	18	Food contact materials	4
Plastic, rubber and resins	17	Childcare articles & toys	4
Soil remediation	15	Cleaning compositions	4
Water and effluent treatment	11	Pharmaceuticals	3
Electronic devices	10	Personal care products	3
Automotive	9	Food additives	1
Pesticides	7	Household applications	1

4.2.5 Category: Sectors/industrial branches

Concerning sectors/industrial branches, a total of 14 different keywords were identified, as shown in Table 8. Announced regulatory actions that refer to the chemical industry represent 37 entries. After that, textile production with 26 entries, production of plastic and rubber with 23 entries, the electronic industry with 14 entries, the food production industry with 13 entries and building and construction with 9 entries, follow. These 6 out of 14 keywords cover a total of 122 out of 134 counted instances in the analyzed actions of the EU strategies. Chemical industry, textile production and the production of plastic and rubber represent 86 of these entries alone. With that, corresponding opportunities can be expected in those sectors/industrial branches. Once more, cosmetics are only represented by two occurrences and the pharmaceuticals industry only by three occurrences respectively in the EU strategies.

Table 8: Category of Sectors/industrial branches and corresponding frequencies of keywords within analyzed EU action plans and strategies

Sectors/industrial branches			
Chemical industry	37	Cosmetics	2
Textile production	26	Energy sector	2
Production of plastic and rubber	23	Aerospace	1
Electronic industry	14	Machinery and equipment	1
Food production industry	13	Manufacture of metal products	1
Building and construction	9	Mining	1
Pharmaceuticals industry	3	Oil & gas industry	1

4.2.6 Category: General scope

Finally, Table 9 lists occurrence frequencies related to the general scope of the actions within the EU action plans and strategies. There is a total of 7 keywords. Circular economy with 70 entries is counted the most by far. This is of no surprise, since two strategy documents are dedicated to circularity and recycling – which indicates regulatory opportunities that might present themselves related to recycling, circularity and the concentration of chemicals residing inside materials. It is worth mentioning though, that substitution of chemicals, with 12 counted entries, and attempts at regulatory harmonization, with only 4 counted entries, were not well represented across the actions of the EU strategies. This could indicate a lack of focus from the EU in comparison to the other keywords and therefore might constitute another potential regulatory gap.

Table 9: Category of General scope and corresponding frequencies of keywords within analyzed EU action plans and strategies

General scope	
Circular Economy/Chemical content of (recycled) products	70
Science-Policy Interface, research and monitoring	18
International action	13
Substitution of chemicals	12
Substance grouping	6
Regulatory harmonization	4
Stakeholder cooperation	5

4.2.7 Summary of results

124 actions announced in various EU strategies and action plans were analyzed to identify how often selected keywords appear. Those keywords in order of their occurrence represent focal areas of the EU, where the European Commission has identified a need for reform and therefore constitute regulatory gaps and or opportunities. Opportunities include regulatory action regarding waste, soil and water and measures that concentrate on REACH and the Industrial Emissions Directive. In terms of use, opportunities might present themselves for textiles and upholstery, paper and packaging, plastic, rubber and resins, soil remediation, water and effluent treatment and electronic devices. As for sectors and industrial branches, potential for regulatory action lies within the chemical industry, textile production and the production of plastic and rubber.

With that, based on the counted occurrences of keywords of the analyzed actions of the EU strategy documents, an overlap of potential opportunities of the different categories can be found in relation to circular economy approaches combined with waste, textiles, paper and packaging involving the chemical industry and especially in relation to PFAS. Gaps can be found regarding the regulation of cosmetics and pharmaceuticals, due to a lack of attention in form of a low number of occurrences of the corresponding keyword within the actions of the analyzed EU strategies.

Table 10: Summary of potential gaps and opportunities drawn from EU action plans and strategies

Summary of results	
Potential gaps	Potential opportunities
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Substance groups/substances: Lack of direct regulatory intentions General scope: Lack of efforts in regard to harmonization efforts and the substitution of chemicals Cosmetics Regulation, pharmaceutical industry and pesticides have a lack of focus on PMT/vPvM substances 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Aims: Waste, soil and water policies Legislation: REACH, Industrial Emissions Directive Use: Textiles and upholstery, paper and packaging, plastic, rubber and resins, soil remediation, water and effluent treatment, electronic devices Sectors and industrial branches: Chemical industry, textile production and the production of plastic and rubber. Substance groups/substances: PFAS as a regulatory gateway for PMT/vPvM substances General scope: Circular Economy

4.3 Report 2 conclusion

Report 2 identified potential regulatory gaps and opportunities for PMT/vPvM substances, which can be used for subsequent substance-specific research of the European legal framework for chemicals and the development of suitable policy options. The analysis of EU strategies and action plans with relevance for PMT/vPvM substances showed more nuanced findings regarding regulatory gaps and opportunities identified by uncovering areas where the European Commission is aware of shortcomings and is focusing on change. Here, opportunities in relation to circular economy approaches combined with waste, textiles, paper and packaging, possibly involving the chemical industry and PFAS as a substance group (and potential regulatory gateway) were identified. Plastics, soil remediation, water and effluent treatment and electronic devices constitute other areas that offer opportunities. Also, affirming the findings of the RMOA analysis, one of the legal pillars of the European chemical regulation – REACH – as well as the Industrial Emissions Directive represent a significant area where regulatory action is important. Gaps can be observed in the lack of direct regulatory intentions regarding PMT/vPvM substances, since most EU actions cover these substances only in an indirect, implicit way. There is also a lack of efforts related to harmonization and

substitution of chemicals. Another potential gap in regulation might be existing in regards to cosmetics and pharmaceuticals, based on the amount of PMT/vPvM substances that can be found within corresponding products.

By combining the results of report 1 with the results of report 2, the following regulatory gaps and opportunities for PMT/vPvM substances can be identified in conclusion:

Gaps:

- Delay of revising REACH Article 57 to add PMT and vPvM substances to the list of substances of very high concern,
- Lack of efficiency of authorization attempts related to products being imported into the EU,
- Lack of focus on better harmonization and substitution of chemicals,
- Lack of direct regulatory ambitions specifically targeting PMT/vPvM substances,
- Lack of EU focus on cosmetics and pharmaceuticals with respect to PMT/vPvM substances,
- Data and time constraints lead to short term regulatory action and insufficient long-term regulatory measures (related: slow international regulatory progress).

Opportunities:

- REACH and the Industrial Emissions Directive in terms of legal areas that may progress PMT/vPvM substance regulation,
- First steps for regulating PMT/vPvM substances include SVHC identification, and possibly restriction approaches dependent on time and data constraints,
- PFAS as a regulatory gateway for other PMT/vPvM substance groups,
- Textiles, plastic, paper and packaging as well as the chemical industry in terms of use and sectors that may progress PMT/vPvM substance regulation,
- Waste and circular economy approaches, especially in terms of recycling and the concentration of chemicals residing inside (contaminated) materials.

5 Report 3: Regulatory gaps and opportunities regarding the regulation of PMT/vPvM substances – a case study of 1,2,4-triazoles

5.1 Triazoles and substance grouping

5.1.1 Triazole chemistry

Report 3 takes a look on regulatory gaps and opportunities of PMT/vPvM substances with a more substance-specific focus. Following this approach report 3 looks at the case of 1,2,4-triazoles and further explores regulatory opportunities related to substance grouping.

Triazoles are heterocyclic compounds with a five-membered ring of two carbon atoms and three nitrogen atoms with molecular formula $C_2H_3N_3$. In the five membered ring there are two positional arrangements of nitrogen atoms resulting in two isomers: 1,2,3-triazole and 1,2,4-triazole, both of which have two tautomers (Figure 3). Both isomers can accommodate a broad range of substituents (electrophiles and nucleophiles) leading to diverse bioactive molecules. Most triazoles produced or imported in large volumes in the European market are 1,2,4-triazoles. For this reason, the following case study covering regulatory gaps and opportunities focuses on the case of 1,2,4-triazoles.

Figure 3: 1,2,3- and 1,2,4-triazoles

5.1.2 Triazole uses

Triazoles are biologically active compounds commonly used as fungicides and herbicides. Triazoles also have antimicrobial, antiviral, antitubercular, anticancer, anticonvulsant, analgesic, antioxidant, anti-inflammatory, and antidepressant activities. These are also important in organocatalysis, agrochemicals, and materials science.

5.1.3 Substance grouping

Assessing and regulating substances individually is inefficient and more resource intensive than assessing groups of substances. For REACH, this has also been highlighted by ECHA who state that:

“To speed up the identification of chemicals that need regulatory action, authorities may decide to address groups of structurally related substances rather than single substances” (ECHA 2024a).

ECHA believes such a grouping approach would bring consistency and coherence for regulatory actions on similar substances, make it faster to identify substances where regulatory action is needed, support informed substitution by industry, help avoid unnecessary animal testing and enable all available data to be used (ECHA 2024a). The importance of informed substitution can be highlighted by recent examples of regrettable substitution by which a similarly hazardous substance has replaced a substance with known hazardous properties. For instance, for many uses of polychlorinated biphenyls (PCBs), short chain chlorinated paraffins (SCCPs) were used as replacements, which were later found ubiquitous at effect concentrations and were added to the Stockholm Convention in 2017; (Guida et al. 2020; Stockholm Convention 2001; Stockholm Convention 2024). PFOS and PFOA were replaced for certain uses with smaller PFAS, PFBS and GenX respectively, which were identified as substances of very high concern under the European Union's REACH Regulation in 2019 and 2020, respectively (Hale et al. 2020).

To group substances, structural similarities can be used as well as by employing read across approaches. In some cases, it may be prudent to also consider similar technical function, hazardous properties or the presence of a specific constituent of concern. One approach is to identify structurally similar substances from all the registered substances in an inventory, where some seeds are pre-selected whereby other substances that are structurally similar to the seed. This provides a group which can be then further assessed and may eventually require regulatory action. At ECHA substance grouping work began in 2010 focusing on REACH and substances that had enough hazard information to

conclude on the need for, and to initiate, the required regulatory risk management. Those substances that have not been grouped are those without enough hazard information. For each group of substances, authorities then consider whether there is a need to initiate further regulatory risk management activities for the whole group, for a subgroup or for individual substances within the group (ECHA 2024a).

Examples of grouping substances based on structural similarity can be seen for ozone depleting substances under the Montreal Protocol and specific groups of persistent organic pollutants (POPs) under the Stockholm Convention. In addition, in Annex XI section 1.5 of the REACH Regulation, details are given on how groups or categories of substances can be defined and which regulatory actions can be applied (Chirsir et al. 2024; Stockholm Convention 2001; UNEP 1987). It states that “substances whose physicochemical, toxicological) and ecotoxicological properties are likely to be similar or follow a regular pattern as a result of structural similarity may be considered as a group, or ‘category’ of substances” (Regulation (EC) No 1907/2006).

Read across approaches rely on the use of data for a reference substance within a group to predict the properties of another structurally similar substance in the group. This method of read-across relies on justified similarities in structure, toxicokinetic, physicochemical and molecular properties, transformation process/endpoints and other similar data for interpolation and extrapolation of relevant information.

Further to using structural similarities and grouping approaches, substance groups could be defined based on retained moieties or chemical substructures from transformation reactions. In the environment, both biotic and abiotic transformations generally result in transformation products (TPs) with significantly higher mobility than their parent compounds or precursors (Zahn et al. 2024).

5.1.4 Transformation products

Taking the triazole compounds listed in PubChem, 62 have recorded degradation pathways and transformation products (12 Jan 2024) (ref ESEU paper), many of which

are plant production products and biocides (primarily fungicides), and a few are pharmaceuticals. To illustrate this, Table 11 shows selected substances and their harmonized hazard classification (if applicable). Within the 62 degradation pathways there are 233 unique reactions, out of which the triazole moiety is retained in 88% of cases, showing its high stability.

Table 11: Selected substances and their harmonized hazard classification

Substance name	CAS	Health hazards	Environmental hazards
Tetraconazole	112281-77-3	Acute Tox. 4 (H302, H332)	Aquatic Chronic 2 (H411)
Fenbuconazole	114369-43-6	N/A	Aquatic Acute 1 (H400), Aquatic Chronic 1 (H410)
Tebuconazole	107534-96-3	Repr. 2 (H361d), Acute Tox. 4 (H302)	Aquatic Acute 1 (H400), Aquatic Chronic 1 (H410)
Paclobutrazol	76738-62-0	Repr. 2 (H361d), Acute Tox 4 (H302, H332) Eye Irrit. 2 (H319)	Aquatic Acute 1 (H400), Aquatic Chronic 1 (H410)
Triadimenol	55219-65-3	Repr. 1B (H360), Acute Tox. 4 (H302), Lact. (H362),	Aquatic Chronic 2 (H411)
Cyproconazole	94361-06-5	Repr. 1B (H360D), Acute Tox. 3 (H301), STOT RE 2 (H373)	Aquatic Acute (H400), Aquatic Chronic (410)
Propiconazole	60207-90-1	Repr. 1B (H360D), Acute Tox. 4 (H302), Skin Sens. 1 (H317)	Aquatic Acute 1 (H400) Aquatic Chronic 1 (H410)
Pyroxsulam	422556-08-9	Skin Sens. 1(H317)	Aquatic Acute 1 (H400) Aquatic Chronic 1(H410)
1,2,4-triazole	288-88-0	Repr. 1B (H360DF), Acute Tox. 4 (H302), Eye Irrit. 2 (H319)	

Within WP6 “Risk Assessment” of ZeroPM, all the triazoles considered were fungicides and all had the 1,2,4-triazole moiety as a potential degradation product (see Table 12). Indeed, the number of fungicides leading to the formation of 1,2,4-triazole is large and triazole fungicides have a widespread use in agriculture (Aliste et al. 2021). That may explain why 1,2,4-triazole has been detected in groundwater, including in 18 % of Danish groundwater monitoring wells (Thorling et al. 2021). Beside the use of azole fungicides and their potential degradation, 1,2,4-triazole emissions from biocidal products and industrial applications – although not as an active substance by itself – need to be considered as well, as is shown in the sections below.

Table 12: The shared metabolite 1,2,4-triazole for the ZeroPM WP6 triazoles

CAS_Zahl	SMILES	Substance name	Shared Metabolite 1	Shared Metabolite 2	Shared Metabolite 3
112281773	<chem>C1=CC(=C(C=C1Cl)Cl)C(CN2C=NC=N2)COC(C(F)F)(F)F</chem>	Tetraconazole*	1,2,4-triazole	triazole acetic acid	triazole alanine
55179312	<chem>CC(C)(C)C(C(N1C=NC=N1)OC2=CC=C(C=C2)C3=CC=CC=C3)O</chem>	Bitertanol	1,2,4-triazole	triazole acetic acid	triazole alanine
114369436	<chem>C1=CC=C(C=C1)C(CCC2=CC=C(C=C2)Cl)(CN3C=NC=N3)C#N</chem>	Fenbuconazole	1,2,4-triazole	triazole acetic acid	triazole alanine
107534963	<chem>CC(C)(C)C(CCC1=CC=C(C=C1)Cl)(CN2C=NC=N2)O</chem>	Tebuconazole	1,2,4-triazole	triazole acetic acid	triazole alanine
288880	<chem>C1=NC=NN1</chem>	1,2,4-triazole			
119446683	<chem>CC1COC(O1)(CN2C=NC=N2)C3=C(C=C(C=C3)OC4=CC=C(C=C4)Cl)Cl</chem>	Difenoconazole	1,2,4-triazole	triazole acetic acid	triazole alanine
76738620	<chem>CC(C)(C)[C@H]([C@@H])(CC1=CC=C(C=C1)Cl)N2C=NC=N2)O</chem>	Paclobutrazol*	1,2,4-triazole	triazole acetic acid	triazole alanine
55219653	<chem>CC(C)(C)C(C(N1C=NC=N1)OC2=CC=C(C=C2)Cl)O</chem>	Triadimenol	1,2,4-triazole	triazole acetic acid	triazole alanine

* not all sources were conclusive that 1,2,4 triazole was formed from this precursor

1,2,4-triazole is hydrolytically stable and not rapidly degradable (maximum of 26% degradation after 24 days in a ready biodegradation test (OECD TG 301A) and 1% degradation after 28 days in an inherent biodegradation test (OECD TG 302B). In an aerobic degradation study in soil, a half-life of 8 days (best fit kinetics) or 9.5 days (non-linear first order once-compartment kinetics) was determined with NER (non-extractable residues) formation of $\leq 65\%$ applied radioactivity after 120 days of incubation (ECHA 2021). In addition, as is shown in Table 11, 1,2,4-triazole is classified as having the following harmonized hazard classes: Reprotoxic 1B (H360FD), Acute Toxicity 2 (H302), Eye Irritation 2 (H319).

Further work in ZeroPM's WP6 has focused on endocrine disrupting properties of selected triazoles. Specifically targeted were the estrogen receptor (ER), the androgen receptor (AR), the thyroid hormone Receptor (TR), the thyroid hormone distributor protein transthyretin (TTR) and whether there was an effect on the release of steroid

hormones. These results are presented in Table 13 and more details are provided as part of ZeroPM Deliverable 6.3 (Manuscript on the ZeroPM Toxicity toolbox) and a forthcoming peer-reviewed publication (Carrier et al., 2024 under revision).

Table 13: Qualitative results for triazoles selected to be used in ZeroPM WP6: Risk Assessment for endocrine disruption screening

	ER	AR	TR	TTR	Steroidogenesis
Tetraconazole	-	++	-	-	++
Bitertanol	++	++	-	+	++
Fenbuconazole	+	++	-	-	++
Tebuconazole	+	++	-	-	++
Difenoconazole	++	++	++	+	++
Paclotriazol	+	+	-	-	+
Triadimenol	++	+	+	-	+
Cyproconazole	+	+	-	-	++
Propiconazole	+	+	+	-	++
Pyroxsulam	-	-	-	-	-
Benzotriazole	-	-	-	-	-
4-methylbenzotriazole	-	-	-	+	-
5-methylbenzotriazole	-	-	-	-	-
1,2,4-triazole	-	-	-	-	-
Triazole acetic acid	-	-	-	-	-
Triazole alanine	-	-	-	-	-

Source: Carrier et al. 2024 (in prep)

ER = agonism or antagonism towards the Estrogen Receptor (ER)

AR = agonism or antagonism towards the Androgen Receptor (AR)

TR = agonism or antagonism towards the Thyroid hormone Receptor (TR)

TTR = binding to the thyroid hormone distributor protein transthyretin (TTR)

Steroidogenesis = Increased or decreased release of steroid hormones. (progesterone, testosterone, estradiol or cortisol)

The current regulatory status in the European Union of the selected triazoles is presented in Table 14.

Table 14: Regulatory status of selected substances

Substance name	CAS	Status under PPPR	Status under BPR	REACH registration	Tonnage band
Tetraconazole	112281-77-3	Approved for uses as fungicide	N/A	No	N/A
Bitertanol	55179-31-2	Not approved (approval withdrawn in 2013)	N/A	No	N/A
Fenbuconazole	114369-43-6	Not approved (approval expired in 2021)	N/A	Yes – manufacture of PPP active substance (likely for export)	≥ 1 tonne per year
Tebuconazole	107534-96-3	Approved for uses as fungicide and plant growth regulator	Approved for PT07, PT08, PT10. Products authorised only for PT08 wood preservatives.	No	N/A
Difenoconazole	119446-68-3	Approved for uses as fungicide	N/A	No	N/A
Paclobutrazol	76738-62-0	Approved for uses as plant growth regulator	N/A	No	N/A
Triadimenol	55219-65-3	Not approved (approval expired in 2019)	N/A	No	N/A
Cyproconazole	94361-06-5	Not approved (approval expired in 2021)	Not approved (approval for PT08-wood preservatives expired in 2020)	Yes – manufacture of the substance and PPP formulation (production for export)	≥ 1 to < 10 tonnes per year
Propiconazole	60207-90-1	Not approved (approval not renewed in 2018)	Approved for PT07, PT08, PT09. Products authorised only for PT08 wood preservatives.	Yes – formulation of mixture (likely production of BP and PPP for export)	≥ 100 to < 1 000 tonnes per year
Pyroxsulam	422556-08-9	Approved until 04/2025	N/A	No	N/A
4-methylbenzotriazole	29878-31-7	N/A	N/A	No	N/A
5-methylbenzotriazole	136-85-6	N/A	N/A	Yes - manufacture of electronic and optical equipment	≥ 1 to < 10 tonnes per year
1,2,4,-triazole	288-88-0	N/A	N/A	Yes - manufacture and use as intermediate	≥ 1 to < 10 tonnes per year
Triazole acetic acid	28711-29-7	N/A	N/A	No	N/A
Triazole alanine	114419-45-3	N/A	N/A	No	N/A

Sources: ECHA 2024b; ECHA 2024c; European Commission 2024).

5.2 Comparison of the current regulatory status of triazoles in biocides, plant protection products and pharmaceuticals legislation

5.2.1 Research Approach

Given the complex environmental pathways through which triazoles can enter ecosystems – encompassing a wide range of uses – a legislative review of various relevant legal areas was carried out. This approach enables the identification of potential regulatory gaps and opportunities regarding triazoles, including their metabolites and degradation products.

To assess the current legislative landscape, a qualitative approach was employed, involving consultations with experts from different sections within the German Environment Agency (UBA). These experts are actively engaged in shaping and enforcing regulations within their respective legal areas, making them well-positioned to provide insights into current regulation regarding triazoles.

The analysis focuses on the three primary legal areas mentioned above relevant to triazoles: biocides (consultations provided by UBA section IV 1.2 Biocides), plant protection products (consultations provided by UBA section IV 1.3-2 Environmental Exposure and Groundwater Risks Plant Protection Products), and pharmaceuticals (consultations provided by UBA section IV 2.2 Pharmaceuticals). The legal areas were selected based on their potential contributions to environmental triazole emissions, either directly through active substances or indirectly via precursors and or metabolites. To identify regulatory gaps and opportunities, the responses from each section were examined for notable aspects, such as regulatory provisions, enforcement challenges, and emerging concerns. Comparisons across the three legal areas aimed to highlight commonalities and differences in the regulation of triazoles, providing a basis for further exploration of cross-sectoral synergies or inconsistencies.

Specifically, the experts were asked whether current regulation already covers PMT and vPvM substances in their respective legal areas – even if only indirectly, such as through new hazard classifications under CLP. The experts were also questioned about their perspectives on triazoles as intermediates or degradation products within their respective

legislative areas. To compare the legislative status of triazole regulation across biocides, plant protection products, and pharmaceuticals, a list of questions was developed (Table 15).

Table 15: Questions regarding the legislative status of triazoles for biocides, plant protection products and pharmaceuticals answered by experts of UBA

Question:
Are triazoles that form 1,2,4-triazoles as a metabolite regulated in your jurisdiction, and if so, how?
Is 1,2,4-triazole considered as a metabolite in the assessment of your enforcement?
To what extent does the current regulation recognise that 1,2,4-triazole is a PMT/vPvM substance?
Do PMT/vPvM properties currently play a role in the regulatory process? Is it foreseeable that this will change in the future? Is there a need?
With regard to emissions of triazoles that degrade to 1,2,4-triazole: Do you see a need for further action (also outside of your enforcement-specific regulations)?
As the responsible specialised unit, how do you assess the relevance of environmental inputs of 1,2,4-triazole through the use of triazole-based fungicides and antimycotics? Can you describe the pathways of entry into the environment?
Are there any further data/findings/suggestions/ideas on the topic of triazoles that you could share with us from the perspective of your section?
Do you have any additional comments?

5.2.2 Triazoles accounted for in biocide legislation:

Regulation (EU) no 528/2012 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 22 May 2012 concerning the making available on the market and use of biocidal products (thereafter Biocidal Products Regulation or BPR) is responsible for regulating substances used as biocides within the European Union. Active substances covered by this regulation need approval for use in biocidal products within the EU. For the purposes of the regulation, products are categorised into product types (PT). In general, according to these product types, triazoles are mainly used as film preservatives (PT 7), wood preservatives (PT 8), preservatives to protect fibre, leather, rubber and polymerised materials (PT 9) and as construction material preservatives (PT 10). Therefore, the emission pathways are mainly present in urban areas (UBA Section IV 1.2 Biocides 2024). For example, triazoles are very important as wood preservatives, so a high number of products containing these substances exist. Emissions from the above-

mentioned products into the environment generally can take place through the following pathways according to UBA section IV 1.2:

- Direct emission to surface water/sediment
- Direct emission to soil → groundwater
- Direct emission to the sewage treatment plant (STP) → surface water/sediment
- Direct emission to the STP → sewage sludge → agricultural soil → groundwater/surface water

1,2,4-triazole is often detected in monitoring studies, such as in the waste-water-treatment-plant monitoring-project of UBA (Fuchs et al. 2020). Further, the substance was prioritized within a prioritization scheme for biocidal substances from UBA section IV 1.2 Biocides, which was invented for monitoring purposes (UBA 2017). Therefore, it is assumed that triazoles and their metabolite 1,2,4-triazole get into all environmental matrices.

In terms of addressing the legal coverage of triazoles forming metabolites, the authorisation of biocides in the EU according to the Biocidal Products Regulation is a two-step procedure. The active substances of biocidal products are first evaluated in an EU level procedure for each product type (PT) and taken up on a “positive” list of approved substances. Only then, can applications for authorisation of biocidal products which contain substances on the list, be submitted in the EU Member States. Before a biocide substance or biocidal product is authorised for sale it must be subjected to an environmental risk assessment, because biocides are a potential hazard to the environment and the health of humans and animals. This procedure was also done for the three triazoles from Table 14 that form 1,2,4-triazoles as metabolites which are propiconazole (PT 7, 8 and 9; all currently approved), tebuconazole (PT 7, 8, 10; all currently approved, PT8 – renewal in progress) and cyproconazole (PT 8, expired since 2020). Results for these three environmental risk assessments can be found at ECHA's website for information on biocides (ECHA 2024b).

Manufacturers are required to submit comprehensive dossiers for active substances containing information on the efficacy, toxicity and environmental fate and behaviour as well as information on metabolites (UBA Section IV 1.2 Biocides 2024). These

dossiers serve as the basis for a detailed risk assessment, considering all potential risks to the environment. Criteria for the evaluation of dossiers are laid out in Article 19 of the Biocidal Regulation (Regulation (EU) No 528/2012). It includes the assessment of relevant metabolites such as 1,2,4-triazoles to ensure that no unacceptable risks exist. This refers to the BPR Guidance Volume IV Part A (2022) and B+C (2017). An environmental risk assessment must be carried out for the relevant compartments for all so-called major metabolites. A major metabolite is present if the metabolite is formed in amounts of $\geq 10\%$ of the active substance at any time during the degradation studies investigated, if the metabolite occurs in quantities of $\geq 5\%$ at two consecutive sampling points, or if the maximum formation has not yet been reached at the end of the study but still accounts for $\geq 5\%$ of the active substance at the last time point. 1,2,4-triazole was identified as a major metabolite in soil for the active substances propiconazole (PT 7, 8 and 9), tebuconazole (PT 7, 8, 10) and cyproconazole (PT 8). An environmental risk assessment of the metabolite was therefore carried out for propiconazole and cyproconazole. During the risk assessment of tebuconazole it was concluded that the ecotoxicity of the metabolite 1,2,4-triazole is significantly lower than that of tebuconazole for both the aquatic and terrestrial environment, so that the metabolite is not further considered in the environmental risk assessment (ECHA 2018; UBA Section IV 1.2 Biocides 2024). After an active substance is approved, each specific biocidal product containing that substance must also undergo a detailed assessment and authorisation procedure. It should be noted that the approach to assess the risk of active substances, as well as the authorisation of biocidal products, is regularly reviewed to consider new information. The BPR stipulates that active substances are approved for a maximum of 10 years initially (article 4) and up to 15 years upon renewal (article 12), while biocidal products are authorised for up to 10 years (article 17) (Regulation (EU) No 528/2012).

The newly established PMT/vPvM hazard classes will be applied to hazard-based assessments for classification and labelling under CLP, based on the revision of CLP in May 2023 (Regulation (EC) No 1272/2008; European Commission 2023b). Currently, the PMT and vPvM hazard classes do not apply to biocides. This is due to a two-year transition period, after which biocidal active substances (May 2025) and products (May

2026) will also be subject to the assessment according to the new CLP Regulation. In addition, the PMT/vPvM hazard classes are not laid down directly in the Biocidal Products Regulation (Regulation (EU) No 528/2012). For this reason, at the moment, it is under discussion if such a classification would have any direct regulatory consequences for the approval of active substances in the EU or for the authorization of biocides in the future. However, substance properties regarding degradation and distribution behaviour are always considered in the environmental risk assessment.

Currently, the P criterion is not met for the three biocidal active substances propiconazole (Soil DT50 = 115 d at 12°C), cyproconazole (Soil DT50 = 18.09 d at 12°C) and tebuconazole (DT50 not yet derived and postponed to renewal) according to valid assessment reports. However, there are some contrasting views. For the water-sediment system ECHA acknowledges the P criterion met by considering cyproconazole as vP in reference to the REACH registration dossier and based on the corresponding simulated half-life in fresh-water sediment exceeding 180 days (ECHA 2024d) Though during renewal of the approval of propiconazole an agreed adjustment of temperature correction of DT50 values needs to be considered which will most likely result in the conclusion that 1,2,4-triazole fulfils the vP criterion based on the water-sediment system (UBA Section IV 1.2 Biocides 2024; University of Hertfordshire 2024).

5.2.3 Triazoles accounted for in plant protection products legislation

Plant protection products in the EU, including all those containing or transforming to 1,2,4-triazole, are regulated primarily by Regulation (EC) No 1107/2009 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 21 October 2009 concerning the placing of plant protection products on the market and repealing Council Directives 79/117/EEC and 91/414/EEC (thereafter Plant Protection Products Regulation or PPPR. This includes metabolites of chemicals used as plant protection products.

Here, the chemical family of triazoles comprises the group ofazole fungicides in the field of plant protection products (PPPs), which form 1,2,4-triazole as a common metabolite in soil. Table 16 shows an overview about PPPs substances that areazole

fungicides and that can form 1,2,4-triazoles as well as their respective relevance in terms of the amount of triazole that might be formed in soil. Four active substances that form 1,2,4-triazol in relevant amounts in soil are currently in the process of re-evaluation for renewed approval (UBA Section IV 1.3-2 Environmental Exposure and Groundwater Risks Plant Protection Products 2024).

Table 16: PPPs active substances that are azole fungicides in relation to forming 1,2,4-triazole

PPP active substances approved within the EU that form 1,2,4-triazole in relevant amounts in soil*	PPP active substances that do not form 1,2,4-triazoles in soil or only in irrelevant amounts	PPP active substances that are currently not approved for use within the EU
Difenoconazole	Bromuconazole	Cyproconazole
Mefentrifluconazole	Hymexazol	Epoxiconazole
Metconazole	Paclobutrazol	Fluquinconazole
Penconazole	Prothioconazole	Hexaconazole
Tebuconazole	Tetraconazole	Ipconazole
	Thiabendazole	Myclobutanil
	Triticonazole	Propiconazole
		Triadimenol

Source: UBA Section IV 1.3-2 Environmental Exposure and Groundwater Risks Plant Protection Products 2024
*Criteria related to occurrence in soil according to SANCO/211/2000 - rev.11, 21. October 2011 (European Commission, Health & Food Safety Directorate – General 2021)

Noteworthy is that in the case of metabolites (this includes all degradation products that are formed either in organisms or in the environment), the EU plant protection legislation differentiates between relevant metabolites (rM) and non-relevant metabolites (nrM) in the assessment of groundwater as detailed below.

- rM: Metabolites for which biological activity or a particular (genetic) toxic, ecotoxic, harmful or mutagenic effect has been demonstrated are to be assessed as relevant metabolites (rM) under plant protection law. They therefore have a higher or comparable risk to the parent substance (active substance).
- nrM: Metabolites for which no higher or comparable risk to the parent substance (active substance) can be demonstrated are to be regarded as non-relevant metabolites (nrM). They may nevertheless have a certain biological as well as (eco)toxicological effect.

Since 1,2,4-triazole has been classified as toxicologically relevant with Repr. 1B it is therefore to be assessed as rM in the context of plant protection product legislation (Commission Delegated Regulation (EU) 2021/849). Following this, in the authorisation procedure, direct leaching into the groundwater after soil passage is considered individually for each active substance and each crop applied for. As relevant metabolites

are treated in the same way as active substances in plant protection legislation, the same threshold values and decision criteria apply to them. For rM, the modelled expected concentrations in groundwater must therefore not exceed a limit value of 0.1 µg/L (European Commission, Health & Food Safety Directorate – General 2021). After classification as rM, harmonised EU-wide endpoints for degradation and sorption in soil (DT50, K_{Foc}) were derived for the assessment of the metabolite 1,2,4-triazole in 2011, which have since been used in the groundwater modelling for the individual active substances. A subsequent official review for Germany, in response to an Art. 44 procedure under EU Regulation 1107/2009 (withdrawal or amendment of an authorization) from Denmark in December 2021, found that not all azoles are yet regulated regarding 1,2,4-triazole (e.g. PPP registrations before 2014, such as tebuconazole). Other azole fungicides are regularly undergoing re-evaluation in the EU approval procedure (e.g. difenoconazole, metconazole), which leads to the expectation of a review of the authorisations of PPPs with these active substances in the near future and thus further considerations of 1,2,4-triazole in risk assessment (UBA Section IV 1.3-2 Environmental Exposure and Groundwater Risks Plant Protection Products 2024).

Also of note is the amount of 1,2,4-triazole formed in soil which varies for different active substances. For this reason, plant protection product legislation considers different formation rates for each active substance for groundwater modelling. In general, according to SANCO/221/2000-rev.11 a groundwater assessment is carried out for a metabolite if the metabolite occurs with the following criteria in soil degradation studies (laboratory or field):

- $\geq 10\%$ or
- $\geq 5\%$ at two consecutive points in time or
- $\geq 5\%$, but increasing at the end of the study

For the group of azole fungicides, there are also active substances for which these criteria for 1,2,4-triazole are not triggered and therefore the metabolite is not considered in groundwater assessments (see Table 16). One example of this is prothiconazole. Also, as part of current EU renewal approval processes for active substances (e.g. difenoconazole, metconazole), it was determined that the adsorption data for 1,2,4-

triazole used in the modelling to date were no longer considered valid and a data gap regarding new data was identified (UBA Section IV 1.3-2 Environmental Exposure and Groundwater Risks Plant Protection Products 2024). The K_{Foc} value is a sensitive parameter in groundwater modelling and is relevant for the calculation of predicted environmental concentrations in groundwater (PEC_{gw}).

According to UBA Section IV 1.3-2 and therefore from a German perspective, when applying PPPs, two entry paths into groundwater can be distinguished: (1) direct leaching in unsaturated soil and (2) bank filtration from surface waters. After the application of PPPs, the entry pathways (a) runoff, (b) drainage, (c) spray drift and (d) volatilisation/deposition can be assessed in surface water. The input into the soil is calculated as part of the authorization process for PPPs. In addition to PPPs, 1,2,4-triazole is contained in fertilisers as a nitrification inhibitor to reduce nitrogen emissions into the environment as well. Although 1,2,4-triazole has now been replaced as an additive in fertilizers available in Germany, the 1,2,4-triazole containing product ENSINplus from a Slovakian company is still available on the European market. With this, additional entry paths into groundwater and surface water are possible (UBA Section IV 1.3-2 Environmental Exposure and Groundwater Risks Plant Protection Products 2024). However, fertilizers are not covered by the plant protection product Regulation. Instead, they are regulated by Regulation (EU) 2019/1009 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 5 June 2019 laying down rules on the making available on the market of EU fertilizing products. However, there is no separate legal framework for the placing on the market of urease and nitrification inhibitors, either at national level or at EU level, where only inhibitors are regulated. They are regulated as components of mineral fertilisers or as additives to organic fertilisers in the relevant legislation. Manufacturers can choose to have their products approved nationally or through the EU Fertiliser Product Regulation mentioned above as part of a conformity assessment.

Monitoring data for 1,2,4-triazoles in plant protection products are scarce. Therefore, since 2019 Germany included 1,2,4-triazoles in the ‘Recommendation list for the monitoring of plant protection product metabolites in German groundwater’ (Umweltbundesamt 2022). Further monitoring concepts like detection procedures

(“Fundaufklärungsverfahren”) are currently being carried out to clarify the causes of findings of $> 0.1 \mu\text{g/L}$ of 1,2,4-triazole in groundwater in Germany. High frequency of detections of 1,2,4-triazole $>0.1 \mu\text{g/L}$ in groundwater were recorded by LAWA (‘Bund/Länder-Arbeitsgemeinschaft Wasser’) for Germany in the years 2017 to 2021 with relatively few monitoring sites investigated. Groundwater monitoring studies on 1,2,4-triazole have also been conducted in France (since 2019) and Denmark (PLAP). Here, findings of 1,2,4-triazole $> 0.1 \mu\text{g/L}$ were found in some cases (UBA Section IV 1.3-2 Environmental Exposure and Groundwater Risks Plant Protection Products 2024). While the findings from public groundwater monitoring are very difficult to attribute to possible sources, targeted monitoring from France and Denmark as well as some findings from “Fundaufklärungsverfahren” indicate that in groundwater concentrations $> 0.1 \mu\text{g/L}$ are a possible result of the use of azole fungicides as PPPs.

In terms of the legislative framework for PMT/vPvM substances under CLP, the Plant Protection Product Regulation currently makes no reference to the categorisation of substances as PMT/vPvM substances. For this reason, PMT/vPvM classification also plays no role in the approval of active substances in the EU or in the authorisation of PPPs. It is not foreseeable that this will change in the future. According to UBAs section IV 1.3-2 for Environmental Exposure and Groundwater Risks Plant Protection Products, classification of substances as PMT/vPvM substances might not be suitable as an exclusion criterion in the context of hazard-based regulation of plant protection products, since classification would affect a very high proportion of PPP active substances. As intended PPP applications already have to be assessed for their potential of groundwater contamination via the entry pathways relevant in agriculture, there is already a risk assessment pathway related to this specific use. Besides, some PPPs and/or their transformation products are known to actually leach into groundwater even if they do not meet the PMT/vPvM criteria. For instance, active substances and metabolites of PPPs that would not be categorised as persistent based on the P criterion (and therefore not as PMT substances) can also leach into groundwater if they have particularly poor sorption properties and are emitted in substantial quantities. The necessity of an assessment of groundwater hazard potential of a PPP substance solely on the basis of its classification as a PMT/vPvM substance could therefore be called into question. Instead,

UBA section IV 1.3-2 points to the currently required quantitative risk assessment for each intended use of a PPP. This covers each approval of an active substance and each authorization of a PPP. Still, for hazard-based assessment in the course of classification and labelling according to the CLP Regulation, the concept will be applied in the future (Regulation (EC) No 1272/2008), to protect for uses outside of PPP, such as for uses falling under REACH. Further, for downstream water regulators/drinking water producers, it is of relevance to know which substances pose a high risk for groundwater contamination, and which of them are hazardous as well as difficult to remove from the water supply.

5.2.4 Triazoles accounted for in pharmaceutical legislation:

EU pharmaceutical legislation differentiates between medicinal products for human use and veterinary medicinal products. While EU legislation covering pharmaceuticals for human use is, for the most part, based on Directive 2001/83/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council of 6 November 2001 on the Community code relating to medicinal products for human use and Regulation (EC) No 726/2004 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 31 March 2004 laying down Community procedures for the authorisation and supervision of medicinal products for human and veterinary use and establishing a European Medicines Agency, veterinary medicinal products are regulated by the Regulation (EU) 2019/6 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 11 December 2018 on veterinary medicinal products. The legislation on medicinal products for human use is currently under revision – legislative proposals were published by the European Commission in April 2023 and are undergoing legislative procedure. According to experts of UBA section IV 2.2 Pharmaceuticals, 1,2,4-triazoles and its occurrences as a transformation product are only of minor importance for pharmaceuticals. It is unclear whether there are any substantial emissions to the environment from active pharmaceutical substances. Though the probability of significant emissions is considered low.

Although there is no evidence for actual environmental entry, UBA section IV 2.2. Pharmaceuticals identified a total of eleven active pharmaceutical ingredients (APIs)

with significant consumption in Germany, that contain 1,2,4-triazole as a structural element (Table 17).

Table 17: Pharmaceuticals that contain 1,2,4-triazole as a structural element

API	CAS Number	ATC Code Level 2 - therapeutic subgroup	1,2,4-triazole is terminal group (release more likely)
Deferasirox	201530-41-8	All other therapeutic products (V03)	yes
Rizatriptan	144034-80-0	Analgesics (N02)	yes
Aprepitant	170729-80-3	Antiemetics and antinauseants (A04)	no
Fluconazole	86386-73-4	Antimycotics for systemic use (J02)	yes
Itraconazole	84625-61-6	Antimycotics for systemic use (J02)	yes
Posaconazole	171228-49-2	Antimycotics for systemic use (J02)	yes
Voriconazole	137234-62-9	Antimycotics for systemic use (J02)	yes
Maraviroc	376348-65-1	Antivirals for systemic use (J05)	yes
Sitagliptin	486460-32-6	Drugs used in diabetes (A10)	no
Letrozole	112809-51-5	Hormone antagonists and related agents (L02)	yes
Trazodone	19794-93-5	Psychoanaleptics (N06)	no

Among these APIs Sitagliptin, used to treat diabetes, has with 40-50 t/year by far the highest consumption in Germany and could theoretically release 7-8 tonnes of 1,2,4-triazole. Based on its structure though, 1,2,4-triazole is an unlikely degradation product. Fluconazole, a fungicide, is the API with highest consumption among the APIs, that could theoretically release 1,2,4-triazole. However, its consumption is two orders of magnitude lower compared with Sitagliptin in Germany. Substantial environmental entries are considered unlikely, based on a QSAR tool from the Swiss EAWAG with which degradation products, including their approximate formation probability, can be

predicted (EAWAG 2024; UBA Section IV 2.2 Pharmaceuticals 2024). Possible entry pathways into the environment in the case of medicinal products for human use could occur via the sewage treatment plants, where hydrophobic compounds will most likely adsorb to a large extent on the clear sludge. This can be spread on agricultural land. In the case of medicinal products for veterinary purposes in regards to food-producing animals, emissions might occur via the spreading of liquid manure on agricultural land. In addition, diffuse inputs via excretions from domestic and small animals in urban and rural areas are also a theoretical possibility.

Metabolites (as substances formed during metabolism) and transformation products (as substances formed by environmental degradation) are generally not regulated in the context of environmental risk assessments (ERA) for pharmaceuticals. In most cases, the regulatory framework is focusing primarily on the parent pharmaceutical compound instead on metabolites or transformation products.

For pharmaceuticals intended for human use, one exception to this general approach involves intended metabolism. In the case of so-called prodrugs, where the active metabolite is a critical component of the drug's design, the regulatory evaluation extends to include the pharmacological active metabolites, but – according to UBA section IV 2.2 Pharmaceuticals – 1,2,4-triazole is not a leaving group in such an intended metabolism. Another potential exception arises through the total residue approach. Initially, for the ERA the total consumed amount of the pharmaceutical substance is considered. If during this process, a potential environmental risk is identified, it is possible to perform an ERA for each identified metabolite representing more than 10%, but according to UBA section IV 2.2 Pharmaceuticals there is no documented instance for this approach.

For pharmaceuticals intended for veterinary use, the ERA requirement can be waived altogether if all metabolites are below 5%. Furthermore, metabolites that account for less than 10% of the dose can be excluded from the overall risk calculation. As with medicinal products for human use, this regulatory mechanism is seldom invoked, and the formation of 1,2,4-triazole as a metabolite in veterinary pharmaceuticals is

considered unlikely. In case that transformation products are formed in degradation tests, those transformation products must be identified. However, there are no regulatory consequences of such identification, which leads to less ambitious assessments in terms of identification of transformation products. In addition, a particular challenge in identifying transformation products, such as 1,2,4-triazole, stems from the reliance on radioactive labelling during environmental degradation tests. If the label is not incorporated into the 1,2,4-triazole structure, the compound may not be detected, which explains why 1,2,4-triazole has yet to be identified as a transformation product of any pharmaceutical compound.

In current regulation, the M-criterion of PMT/vPvM hazard classification is not considered in pharmaceutical legislation. Medicinal products are not covered by the CLP Regulation. However, a draft for the revised EU pharmaceutical legislation proposes that PMT/vPvM active substances should no longer be freely available for sale (this also applies to active substances that are PBT/vPvB) (European Commission 2023a; UBA Section IV 2.2 Pharmaceuticals 2024). Whether and when this will be implemented remains to be seen.

5.3 Report 3 conclusion: Regulatory gaps and opportunities for triazoles in biocides, plant protection products, and pharmaceuticals legislation

This overall consideration of the legal status of triazoles within biocides products, PPPs and pharmaceutical products, reveals a handful of regulatory gaps and opportunities. First, in the case of biocides multiple emission pathways and a wide use with various applications (e.g., wood preservatives and film preservatives) can be found. Regulatory gaps and opportunities include the following:

- **Regulation of metabolites:** 1,2,4-triazole has been identified as a major metabolite of several triazole-based biocides. During the environmental risk assessment, the ecotoxicity of 1,2,4-triazole is deemed as lower than that of its parent compounds. However, this might lead to reduced attention during regulatory evaluations and could

represent a potential gap as the cumulative effects of metabolites might not be comprehensively regulated.

- **PMT/vPvM classification:** The newly established PMT and vPvM hazard classes under the CLP Regulation do not apply to biocides during the current two-year transition period. Only after this period, will biocidal substances be subject to the classification. This creates the opportunity of using the given window in time to make sure the new hazard classes will be applied and defined properly in the context of biocides. Correct application of the hazard classification could influence future risk assessments for triazoles. Attention has to be paid to a) the fact that the PMT/vPvM classification is not laid down in the BPR, b) the current uncertainty about potential direct regulatory consequences for the authorization process and c) the fact that substance properties related to degradation and distribution behaviour impact environmental risk assessment.
- **Re-evaluation of the P criterion for 1,2,4-triazoles in the case of Propiconazole:** In terms of an adjustment of temperature correction of DT_{50} values.
- **Data gaps for biocide-relevant pathways:** While 1,2,4-triazole has been detected in various environmental matrices, including surface water and groundwater, a data gap lies not in monitoring itself, but in the tracking of biocide-relevant entry pathways. While monitoring data can be used as supplementary information during enforcement, a more targeted approach to tracing biocide-specific pathways is needed to better understand the environmental impact of triazoles and their metabolites, offering another regulatory opportunity.

Second, the following gaps and opportunities can be found for the legal area of plant protection products:

- **Data gaps in monitoring:** Similar to biocides legislation, gaps in relation to monitoring efforts are present for plant protection products as well. Although Germany and other EU member states have initiated monitoring efforts for 1,2,4-triazole in groundwater, such efforts are still scarce and incomplete. A combination of an absence of corresponding monitoring obligations and lacking monitoring implementations can be considered a regulatory gap. Expanding current monitoring programs, establishing new monitoring programs (particularly in high-exposure agricultural areas, and with a targeted focus to identify the sources of 1,2,4-triazole leaching) and refining risk assessments based on new data can be considered a corresponding opportunity for better future regulation. Following this, new data is necessary for adsorption data for 1,2,4-

triazoles used in groundwater modelling for current EU renewal approval processes for active substances as well, since it was determined that current adsorption data is no longer considered valid.

- ▼ **Substance-specific gaps:** A regulatory gap was identified for PPP registrations in Germany before 2014 with tebuconazole, for which the groundwater assessment regarding 1,2,4-triazole is necessary to be reviewed possibly leading to an amendment of authorisations.

Third, regulatory gaps and opportunities identified for pharmaceuticals are as follows:

- **Limited regulation of metabolites and transformation products:** The environmental risk assessments for pharmaceuticals tend to focus on the parent active substances, while metabolites and transformation products, including 1,2,4-triazole, are generally not regulated. Although some exceptions exist (e.g., for prodrugs or substances with significant environmental risk), for the most part the overall regulatory framework does not consider metabolites. Although actual environmental entries are considered unlikely, they can still be considered theoretically feasible. This might translate to another regulatory gap in the environmental assessment of pharmaceuticals.
- **Potential environmental emissions:** Although the actual emissions of triazoles from pharmaceuticals are considered unlikely, eleven active pharmaceutical ingredients (APIs) with significant consumption rates (for Germany) have been identified that contain 1,2,4-triazole as a structural element. However, there is no robust evidence of significant environmental releases based on predictions made by using a QSAR tool from the Swiss EAWAG and transformation products like 1,2,4-triazole have yet to be detected in pharmaceutical degradation studies. Still, while transformation products in degradation tests must be identified, missing regulatory consequences upon identification and the consequential lack of ambitious assessment in this regard constitutes a regulatory gap and an opportunity for emboldening research.
- **PMT/vPvM classification:** Pharmaceuticals are not currently subject to PMT/vPvM classification under the CLP Regulation, but a draft revision of the EU pharmaceutical legislation suggests that active substances that can be classified as PMT/vPvM substances should no longer be freely available for sale. Following up on this proposal represents another opportunity for the regulation of triazoles and for the

pharmaceutical sector to align with emerging environmental hazard-based classifications.

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Appendix A: Hazard classes for PMT/vPvM substances under CLP

Classification criteria for PMT
<p>Persistence:</p> <p>A substance shall be considered to fulfil the persistence criterion (P) in any of the following situations:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> (a) the degradation half-life in marine water is higher than 60 days; (b) the degradation half-life in fresh or estuarine water is higher than 40 days; (c) the degradation half-life in marine sediment is higher than 180 days; (d) the degradation half-life in fresh or estuarine water sediment is higher than 120 days; (e) (e) the degradation half-life in soil is higher than 120 days
<p>Mobility:</p> <p>A substance shall be considered to fulfil the mobility criterion (M) when the log K_{oc} is less than 3. For an ionisable substance, the mobility criterion shall be considered fulfilled when the lowest log K_{oc} value for pH between 4 and 9 is less than 3</p>
<p>Toxicity:</p> <p>A substance shall be considered to fulfil the toxicity criterion (T) in any of the following situations:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> (a) the long-term no-observed effect concentration (NOEC) or EC_x (e.g. EC₁₀) for marine or freshwater organisms is less than 0,01 mg/l; (b) the substance meets the criteria for classification as carcinogenic (category 1A or 1B), germ cell mutagenic (category 1A or 1B), or toxic for reproduction (category 1A, 1B, or 2) according to sections 3.5, 3.6 or 3.7; (c) there is other evidence of chronic toxicity, as identified by the substance meeting the criteria for classification as specific target organ toxicity after repeated exposure (STOT RE category 1 or 2) according to section 3.9; (d) (d) the substance meets the criteria for classification as endocrine disruptor (category 1) for human health or the environment according to sections 3.11 or 4.2.
Classification criteria for vPvM
<p>Persistence:</p> <p>A substance shall be considered to fulfil the ‘very persistent’ criterion (vP) in any of the following situations:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> (a) the degradation half-life in marine, fresh or estuarine water is higher than 60 days; (b) the degradation half-life in marine, fresh or estuarine water sediment is higher than 180 days; (c) the degradation half-life in soil is higher than 180 days.
<p>Mobility:</p> <p>A substance shall be considered to fulfil the ‘very mobile’ criterion (vM) when the log K_{oc} is less than 2. For an ionisable substance, the mobility criterion shall be considered fulfilled when the lowest log K_{oc} value for pH between 4 and 9 is less than 2.</p>

Source: European Commission (2022) and Regulation (EC) No 1272/2008

Appendix B: RMOA case analysis

Case 1: PFBS

The first RMOA of a PMT/vPvM substance that will be discussed covers perfluorobutane sulfonic acid, its salts and related substances (PFBS, CAS No. 375-73-4 & 59933-66-3; EC No. 206-793-1). The RMOA was submitted by Norway. PFBS can be assigned to the group of per- and polyfluoroalkyl substances (PFAS) and with that, shares concerns of persistence, mobility and toxicity for human health and the aquatic environment – including drinking water, that a lot of its peer substances invoke (Norwegian Environment Agency 2018). It is described as a short-chained PFAS that is one of the dominating PFAS detected in rivers or sea water in Europe according to the RMOA.

To counteract the concerns of PFBS, multiple regulatory actions are proposed in the RMOA. Proposals for regulatory action are based a) on PFBS being an extremely persistent substance that, according to the RMOA, fulfills the REACH criteria of P and vP and for which degradation under environmental relevant conditions is not expected. Further, b) it is a mobile substance that is highly aqueous soluble with a low adsorption potential, which leads it to reaching (drinking) water bodies. This has been proven by several (European) monitoring studies. In terms of mobility, PFBS also shows long-range-transport capabilities, since it has been found even in remote areas. In addition, c) potential exposure and d) toxicological concerns for potential long-term effects play a role for the regulatory proposals of the RMOA as well. Low, but increasing concentrations of PFBS have been found in human tissue and wildlife in EU as well as non-EU populations. According to the RMOA humans and or herbivores might suffer adverse effects by the substance potential for protein binding, which is toxicological relevant. PFBS is able to accumulate and concentrate in water-rich edible parts of plants. The RMOA states that PFBS may cause organ-damage (liver, kidneys, stomach, hematological system), the danger of underestimating long-term effects for humans in comparison to animal test-data due to the higher half-life of PFBS in humans, potential endocrine disrupting properties and potential immunotoxicology effects (e.g. asthma). However, it is also stated, that data is not

sufficient to meet the CLP criteria for classification at the time of writing the RMOA in 2018. Further, like with many other PMT/vPvM substances, the elimination of PFBS in contaminated water resources by conventional water treatment processes is described as difficult. Even if removal was fully possible, reversing effects on drinking water sources and the aqueous environment might not be possible. Increasing levels of contamination might be a consequence (Norwegian Environment Agency 2018).

Because of all of this and in conjunction with the precautionary principle, the RMOA concludes there is a very high concern and proposes identifying PFBS as a SVHC by applying article 57 (f) of REACH, which constitutes an equivalent level of concern of the substances to PBT or vPvB substances (Regulation (EC) No 1907/2006).

“Taken together, the available data show that PFBS exhibits properties that give rise to an equivalent level of concern to PBT/vPvB substances. PFBS should therefore be identified as a substance of Very High Concern (SVHC) according to REACH article 57 f) and included in the Candidate List” (Norwegian Environment Agency 2018: 5).

As a follow-up measure after identifying PFBS as a SVHC, the RMOA proposes a restriction targeting PFBS, including its salts as well as related substances. Restricting a substance means including it into annex XVII of REACH and therefore manufacture, use and placing on the market are limited or banned in the EU (ECHA 2023c). According to the RMOA, a restriction offers various advantages. First, it covers the possibility of addressing multiple, related substances, being PFBS, its salts and precursors. A similar approach is used in case of regulating PFOA under REACH. Second, a restriction might limit the amount of the substance within articles, which includes imported articles as well. With that, emissions from articles in the EU as a whole, and not only articles originating from the EU, can be reduced via restriction. For PFBS this is especially important as a lot of production and use of PFBS originates from China.

Authorisation is not the preferred regulatory measures for PFBS. Authorisation results in an inclusion of the substances in question into annex XIV of REACH, which means that “Companies that want to continue using a substance included in the Authorisation

List after the sunset date need to prepare an application for authorisation, submit it before the latest application date and have a positive authorisation decision by the European Commission” (ECHA 2023d). Hesitation toward authorisation is due to concerns that stricter regulation based on authorisation procedures for production and or use of PFBS and its related substances in the EU might not actually result in a reduction of overall emissions or alteration of the content of imported articles, but may instead end up merely moving industrial production and use out of the EU. To highlight this, the RMOA noted that a similar shift has been observed for other cases like PFOA.

Aside from SVHC identification and restriction, other, alternative measures have been evaluated by the RMOA. Deemed as an appropriate, complementary non-EU regulatory measure for PFBS is the Stockholm Convention. The Stockholm Convention is an international regime in form of a global treaty that intends to protect human health and the environment from chemicals focusing on POPs – persistent organic pollutants (Stockholm Convention on Persistent Organic Pollutants 2001). The convention requires its participant parties to take measures that prohibit and or eliminate (annex A), restrict (annex B) and reduce emissions of listed substances in terms of production, use, import and export. It also covers management with unintentionally produced POPs (annex C) and waste management. Due to the Stockholm Convention’s focus on a) persistent pollutants and b) pollutants with long-range transport capabilities, its potential for global regulation can be considered when dealing with many PMT/vPvM substances as well – including PFBS and related substances (Norwegian Environment Agency 2018).

Case 2: GenX

The second substance of interest in terms of already regulated PMT/vPvM substances is FRD-902, commonly known as GenX (ammonium 2,3,3,3-tetrafluoro-2-(heptafluoropropoxy) propanoate; EC Number: 700-242-3, CAS Number: 62037-80-3). The corresponding RMOA was written by the Dutch *National Institute for Public Health and the Environment* (RIVM).

According to ECHA, the substance is REACH registered with tonnage between 10 and 100 tons per annum in terms of manufacture or imports in the European economic area. While ECHA has no publicly registered data about consumer and/or professional uses, article service life as well about formulation, re-packing or emission channels into the environment and whether or which chemical products or articles contains or processes the substance in question, some aspects of industrial usage are known. These include the use of GenX as a pH regulator, water treatment product, as well as polymers and plastic products. In these instances, emissions can occur from processing aids at industrial sites (ECHA 2023e). Also, according to the respective RMOA, those industrial uses represent the main concern in terms of environmental emissions.

Similar to PFBS, GenX belongs to the group of short-chained PFAS, which in turn entail a variety of concerns. These concerns are based on a) persistence, mobility and toxicity substance properties and b) on the fact, that FRD-902 dissolves to its anion HFPO-DA, which “the human and environmental health properties and environmental behavior and fate characteristics of FRD-902 are attributed to [...]” (RIVM 2018: 5). It is noteworthy, that other substances, like FRD-903 (used for production of FRD-902) and potassium salt of HFPO-DA can form HFPO-DA in the environment.

The RMOA states that GenX has an extreme persistence and a high-water solubility, an inability to adsorb to soil or sediment and high long-range transport potential supported by various monitoring data. For example, the substance was not only found in the close vicinity of locations with plausible local emission sources, but also far

from such sources. Therefore, the competent authorities responsible for the GenX RMOA expect the substance to widely migrate beyond borders, to contaminate remote and pristine areas and to amass in form of an over-time increasing “constant background pollution and consequently, exposure” (RIVM 2018: 10). On top of this, as it is the case for many PMT/vPvM substances, common remediation techniques are not very effective in terms of removing HFPO-DA from the environment and drinking water because of those properties. For toxicological properties, the RMOA mentions possible adverse effects for e.g. liver or red blood cells that could lead to carcinogenic consequences in organisms (RIVM 2018). In addition, the substance is under assessment as a PBT substance by ECHAs PBT expert group (ECHA 2023f).

In respect to exposure, low concentrations of GenX were found in a variety of sources including drinking water, fish and vegetables. Indirect exposure of the general population through the environment as well as low – but still concerning – concentrations in waste are other possible exposure routes. Adding to this, the RMOA stresses, that HFPO-DA is not the only worrisome PFAS substance to be found in the environment and that multiple of these substances together might lead to aggregated exposure with possible corresponding aggregated adverse effects on human health and the environment, based on similar persistent, mobile and potentially toxic properties.

“Given the apparent toxicity, extreme persistence, very high mobility and exposure to humans and the environment, as well as the uncertain, wide spread and uncontrollable emission at the waste phase, the NL-CA is of the opinion that HFPO-DA and its salts, among which FRD-902, can be considered as a substance of very high concern to human health and the environment” (RIVM 2018: 6).

To cover all relevant substances, to increase transparency and predictability as well as to prevent undesirable substitution, the RMOA suggests for regulatory activities not only to focus on HFPO-DA and FRD-902, but also on its salts, FRD-903 and its potassium salt as well (RIVM 2018). It emphasizes how important it is for substances like GenX, that are very persistent and very mobile, to hurry with decision making and regulation and to not wait to long for higher quality data, since the problem might be a) steadily increasing with time and b) potentially irreversible. Monitoring data supports this by showing widespread detection and increasing amounts of the

substance, found over relatively short spans of time (5-6 years; data from 2012-2018). Following these thoughts, to counteract and regulate the concerns of GenX, the RMOA proposes two core measures.

First, similar to the case of PFBS, for HFPO-DA, its salts, FRD-902, FRD-903 and its potassium salt, a SVHC identification, based on an equivalent level of concern (ELoC) according to article 57 (f) of REACH is viewed as appropriate. An ELoC approach was chosen because at the time of releasing the corresponding RMOA, available information about FRD-902 did not meet the requirements under article 57 (a) to (e) for SVHC identification. SVHC identification for GenX is advantageous as a) there is a possibility that more stringent emission permits could be introduced under annex II of the Industrial Emissions Directive (Directive 2010/75/EU). In addition, SVHC identification b) puts GenX on the ECHA candidate list, which in turn might trigger member specific national legislation and c) helps with uncovering possible emission sources and generates therefore additional data about the substance. This is due to obligations for producers and manufacturers to notify agencies if they are using FRD-902. Also, as soon as articles contain a certain amount of the substance, this has to be communicated as well (RIVM 2018).

Second, authorisation as a follow-up action, by adding GenX to annex XIV of REACH is described as another type of regulatory action after successful SVHC identification. Authorisation measures result in a reduction of the total emissions of the substance. It is possible for industrial actors to apply for exemptions for cases that are deemed safe and/or for which there is no justifiable alternative and “the impact on society of no longer using the substance would be disproportionately high” (RIVM 2018: 11). As stated by the RMOA, for GenX this is especially fitting, since there is only a relatively low number of potential industrial users according to CLP substance notifications, which in turn should result in a corresponding low number of authorisation applications and therefore this enables a record of uses and users to be developed and maintained and facilitates enforcement of regulatory measures as well as “stimulate research and development for substitution” (RIVM 2018: 12). One

possible prospect for an application of authorisation for GenX can be found for waste treatment, since a SVHC identification on its own will have no direct impacts on waste treatment activities, according to the RMOA. Important to note is, that authorisation efforts will only have a limited amount of influence or not help in terms of regulating imported articles. Articles that contain residual amounts of HFPO-DA in form of impurities from production will not be affected. Import of articles will still be possible and production and use outside of Europe will be allowed further. Because of this, the problem might simply move to other countries outside of the EU and no decrease of HFPO-DA emissions might occur as a consequence.

Third, although the RMOA does not formally recommend a restriction per se, it is stated that “the NL-CA is of the opinion that in addition to SVHC identification the need for restriction should be further evaluated in the light of ongoing work on the group of short chain perfluoro substances and restrictions considered in that context“ (RIVM 2018: 14). This is due to the fact that immediate action is needed and a restriction process can take quite some time. Also, a SVHC identification in advance of a restriction is generally the favoured way of processing. With that, the RMOA suggests to concentrate on SVHC identification and general authorisation efforts while gathering more data on GenX to increase chances for successful restriction and plan for a corresponding restriction proposal in parallel, following REACH annex XV. Emphasis is placed upon restriction, since it addresses substances that pose EU-wide concerns and offers a variety of regulatory advantages in comparison to authorisation efforts. The possibility of targeted risk management, like setting emission limits or restricting the maximum allowed residual concentrations, is one of those advantages. Also, a restriction of GenX applies to imported articles as well. This leads a) to potential prevention of importing articles that contain residual amounts of the substance and b) discourages production and use of HFPO-DA outside of Europe, according to the RMOA. In addition, while SVHC identification might trigger member state specific legislation, the extent of legal areas as well as the impact of the measures can vary widely among member states. For that purpose, a restriction represents a much more unified attempt at regulating GenX. It is noteworthy that for

substances with a high tonnage in production and use and with a lot of registrants and or downstream users, that require many applications for authorisation, restriction in comparison with authorisation approaches, offers smoother bureaucratic processes in general. However, with a comparable small number of notifiers, a single registered use-case and a registered tonnage of only 10-100 tonnes per annum this is not the case for FRD-902.

Aside from the above-mentioned proposals for regulatory action, the RMOA discusses other measures as well. The most important of those measures include a) harmonised classification and labelling efforts (CLH), e.g. a potential assignment of the hazard classes STOT RE 2 and or Carc. Cat 2., b) action under the Stockholm Convention and c) further advancements in gathering data and substance evaluation. Not counting a) classification and labelling under annex VI of the CLP regulation, the RMOA regards most of those other measures as inappropriate risk management options. While GenX, according to the NL-CA, could meet concerns that demand worldwide regulation and might fulfill the criteria of the Stockholm Convention, data at the time of release of the RMOA is evaluated as insufficient. In addition, suggesting a course of action involving the Stockholm Convention is deemed as not appropriate, since it would be too time-consuming for a substance that is, based on its immediate concern, in need of decisive and fast regulatory action. With that, the RMOA recommends concentrating regulatory action under CLP and REACH, but also eludes, that measures under the Stockholm Convention could be discussed in parallel.

Regulatory action summarized under a) harmonised classification and labelling (CLH), describes the EU-wide classification and labelling of hazardous substances and mixtures of the highest concern (in terms of carcinogenicity, mutagenicity, reproductive toxicity [CMR], respiratory sensitizers and other selected substances) for protecting human health and the environment by applying adequate risk management and listing the corresponding substances in annex VI of the CLP regulation. It applies to all manufacturers, importers or downstream users (ECHA 2023g). In regards to GenX, no harmonised classification and labelling applies to the substances in

question, at the time the corresponding RMOA was released. This is highlighted when looking at annex VI of the CLP regulation (version April 2023), although the ECHA databank lists the substances as “GHS08: Serious Health Hazard”, which covers Carc. Cat 2 as well as STOT RE 2, but only according to self-classification of companies (ECHA 2023e; Regulation (EC) No 1272/2008). Similar to its suggestion for handling a potential future restriction, the RMOA proposes to gather more data and to initiate action for a CLH for Carc. Cat 2 (“suspected of causing cancer”) in parallel to SVHC identification.

Case 3: Melamine

The third RMOA dealing with PMT/vPvM substances is for Melamine (CAS No. 108-78-1; EC No. 203-615-4). Melamine was evaluated in 2022 by the German Competent Authority (DE CA).

According to information from DE CA, publicly known uses of the substance cover applications in different articles like resins, adhesives, flame retardants, kitchenware, bambooware as well as melaware and for coatings (BAuA 2022). In addition, ECHA's database states multiple routes of possible releases of Melamine into the environment. These include industrial uses and manufacture, which for example can lead to emission by abrasion processes, but also long-lasting indoor as well as outdoor uses, that emit varying amounts of the substance over longer stretches of time. The latter encompasses articles made of metal, wood or plastic like flooring, furniture, toys, textiles, foot-wear, construction materials and electronic equipment, but also certain paper and leather products as well as food packaging and complex machinery like vehicles (personal, boats, trains, planes and more). Metals and textiles containing the substance are often used for covering large surface areas – e.g. for roofs in construction or for carpets or tapestry. Also, widespread use by professional workers for laboratory applications, for coating, as a binding agent or for detergents and paints play a role as well. Furthermore, other uses at an industrial level such as utilization as intermediates or as processing aids are known too (ECHA 2023h). In terms of manufactured and/or imported tonnage into the EU Melamine is registered under REACH with 100 000 to 1 000 000 tonnes per annum.

Similar to the cases of PFBS and GenX, the respective RMOA for Melamine describes the roots of concerns by the substances inherent persistent, mobile and toxic properties and concludes that relevant human health and environmental hazards for Melamine exist. As for other PMT/vPvM substances, concerns account for the possibility of emerging consequences for drinking water resource containment and for the difficulties in terms of remediation. Also, ECHA lists the substance as suspected to

be carcinogenic, as well as under PBT (persistent, bioaccumulative and toxic) assessment and under assessment for endocrine disrupting properties (ECHA 2023h).

To counteract the concerns Melamine poses, multiple regulatory measures are proposed by the RMOA. Again, first and foremost, SVHC identification is recommended due to Melamine's very persistent (vP) and very mobile (vM) properties in the aquatic environment. Article 57 (f), which covers equivalent levels of concern compared to the other criteria laid down in article 57 (a-e) that effect the environment, is used as a basis to tackle the substances PMT/vPvM properties and corresponding environmental and human health concerns. The RMOA justifies the importance of a SVHC identification with a) the formal recognition that hazardous properties of Melamine will be given, b) due to the potential of subsequent risk management options and regulation – in other words regulatory opportunities – that might emerge from SVHC identification, c) because of the early warning function that the SVHC status will have for industry and the consequent incentive to minimize and or substitute emissions of the substance in time and d) SVHC identification opens up certain pathways for better informing consumers and other actors along the industrial supply chain.

To address the reproductive toxicity of Melamine, the second proposal of the RMOA aims at harmonised classification on the basis of an extended one-generation reproduction toxicity study. It is suggested that Melamine is classified under Reproductive toxicity, Repr. 2, H361f (suspected of damaging fertility) under the CLP regulation (BAuA 2022; Regulation (EC) No 1272/2008). *“Because of the histopathological changes and altered sperm cell morphology observed in F0/F1 animals, the aMSCA [author Member State Competent Authority] feels confident that classification for effects on fertility is warranted”* (BAuA 2022: 6). It is noteworthy that RAC already adopted an opinion on the matter of Melamine in terms of classification of the substance for STOT RE 2, H373 (may cause damage to organs through prolonged or repeated exposure) and Carc. 2, H351 (suspected of causing cancer) in December of 2020. A harmonised classification based on human health

might trigger substitution efforts which indirectly cover environmental concerns as well and therefore can be seen an initial risk management option.

Third, summarized under “other union-wide regulatory measures” (BAuA 2022: 7), the introduction of occupational exposure limits for workplaces is suggested. Based on the particular risk of workers that might come into contact with high amounts of Melamine (pure or in mixtures), a recommendation for (sufficiently) decreasing exposure by introducing appropriate risk management measures (RMM) at the workplace, by means of indicative occupational exposure limit values (IOELV), are addressed. IOELV originate from EU Council Directive 98/24/EC on the protection of the health and safety of workers from the risks related to chemical agents at work. Here, article 2(d) states, that ‘Occupational exposure limit value means, unless otherwise specified, the limit of the time-weighted average of the concentration of a chemical agent in the air within the breathing zone of a worker in relation to a specified reference period’ (Directive 98/24/EC: 4). In the case of Melamine, an IOELV can help draw attention to appropriate risk management for workers. IOELV are not binding (BOELV), but merely indicative values for occupational exposure limits. The RMOA stresses that successful implementation needs practical guidelines, that help select appropriate RMMs. For this purpose and for the case of Melamine, the S.T.O.P. principal (Substitution, Technical measures, Organizational measures, Personal protective measures) is referred to by the RMOA.

Further regulatory measures were also discussed, but not seen as appropriate ways to deal with the concerns from Melamine. These measures include actions under the Industrial Emissions Directive like BATs (best available technique) described in BREFs (best available techniques reference documents), other downstream legislation as well as the possibility of a restriction proposal under REACH. The main reasons for deciding against said measure is because they would either take a lot of time or because there are significant uncertainties in terms of risk assessment due to lacking data (BAuA 2022; Directive 2010/75/EU).

“Moreover, the aMSCA [author Member State Competent Authority] expects that the harmonised classification and labelling of melamine and its identification as SVHC will lead to market changes and a certain pressure towards substitution of Melamine also in mattresses. Only if these substitution effects prove to be insufficient, a specific restriction might be required” (BAuA 2022: 6).

Case 4: 1,4-Dioxane

The final RMOA discussed covers 1,4-Dioxane (CAS No. 123-91-1; EC No. 204-661-8), which was evaluated in 2020 by BAuA.

1,4-Dioxane plays a role in multiple sectors including detergents, paints, coatings, adhesives or fragrances. It is contained in articles meant for flooring, in furniture, toys, construction materials, curtains, foot-wear, leather products, paper and cardboard products or electronic equipment, to name just a few. The substance is used as a laboratory chemical, as a pH-regulator, as a component of heat transfer for liquids in closed systems (e.g. cooling liquid for refrigerators), as a processing aid (solvent) and intermediate for industrial use and manufacture (BAuA 2020; ECHA 2023i). “Furthermore, it is an impurity or constituent of substances of high economic impact produced in large annual quantities, e.g. surfactants” (BAuA 2020: 5). According to ECHA, 1,4-Dioxane is manufactured and/or imported in amounts between 1 000 to 10 000 tonnes per annum in the EU (ECHA 2023i). Suggestions for regulatory action derive from the concern of persistent, mobile and toxic (PMT) properties. ECHA recognized 1,4-Dioxane as a carcinogenic substance and it is under PBT assessment as well. The substance is listed under annex VI of CLP for harmonised classification and labelling of hazardous substances – although not based on its persistent and mobile properties, but rather for its carcinogenic properties – and listed in annex II of the Cosmetics Regulation, which prohibits 1,4-Dioxane in cosmetic products (Regulation (EC) No 1223/2009; Regulation (EC) No 1272/2008).

In the RMOA proposed regulatory measures include: First and analogous with the RMOAs of other PMT/vPvM substances covered, SVHC identification based on 1,4-Dioxane’s environmental effects and its (indirect) exposure of the general population (BAuA 2020). The purpose of SVHC identification is to trigger certain communication requirements to consumers and industry alike, as well as to promote substitution according to the RMOA. Again, SVHC identification is based on the substance properties of persistence, mobility and toxicity and on an EloC compared to PBT/vPvB substances, in agreement with article 57 (f) of REACH.

As a potential second step after SVHC identification BauA mentions the possibility of authorization measures but argues that authorization may only help deal with the concerns of 1,4-Dioxane to a limited extent and would be not an effective risk management measure overall. This is due to a) the fact that imported articles would not be covered by such regulatory actions for the most part and b) because of 1,4-Dioxane's unintended low occurrences in mixtures and other substances.

“Authorisation addresses the use of a substance as such as well as in mixtures. However, 1,4-dioxane is also present as an unintended constituent (impurity) in many other substances in relevant concentrations which, although the concentration of the impurities is very low (<0.1%) in sum result in relevant emissions to the environment. Such substances are used in various applications and according to the aMSCAs knowledge contribute significantly to emissions of 1,4-dioxane to the environment“ (BAuA 2020: 5).

Because of this limited influence authorisation measures might have on emissions, the RMOA argues, that imprudent authorisation efforts might even “hamper” later restriction efforts (BAuA 2020).

A second proposal, for a restriction of 1,4-Dioxane covers imported articles as well, although its scope can differ. While a) a general restriction has significance for all products containing 1,4-Dioxane above a certain concentration, the RMOA assesses b) a restriction tailored to the emissions of only specified uses as the more appropriate regulatory choice for dealing with the concerns arising for human health and or the environment. This way, concerns like the occurrence of low concentrations (e.g. impurities in products), that nevertheless contribute to the total amount of 1,4-dioxan emissions, can be addressed by for example setting concentration limits that should not be exceeded (BAuA 2020). Also, a restriction can be used as a tool for increasing occupational safety and health by lowering occupational risks. However, when doing so, hazard as well as exposure is considered, which together have to constitute an “unacceptable risk” (BAuA 2020: 6). Because of this, according to the RMOA, a restriction based on the perspective of occupational safety and health is viewed as premature and therefore not proposed. The reason for this is the data status and outdated IOELVs at the point of writing the RMOA, which impedes an adequate evaluation of 1,4-Dioxan in form of a quantitative risk assessment. A possible re-

evaluation of a restriction based in occupational safety and health in the future is suggested in case other risk management tools fail to achieve their goals.

Finally, some other EU-wide regulatory measures are proposed according to the 1,4-Dioxane RMOA. These include a) to repeal the, according to the RMOA, obsolete IOELV as a basis for risk assessment and install an adequate BOELV, which can be derived from the now in force Carc. 1B classification (“may cause cancer”), in accordance with the Carcinogens and Mutagens Directive (BAuA 2020; Directive 2004/37/EC). In addition, b) updating of the registration dossiers by the corresponding registrants is suggested.

Appendix C: EU strategy and action plan actions and measures

EU-Strategy:	Action/Measure:	Aims at	Legislation	Substance Groups/substances	Use	Sectors/industrial branches	General scope
EU Biodiversity Strategy for 2030. Bringing nature back into our lives (3)	Develop a set of indicators for the progressive reduction of pollution and establish baselines to help monitor progress.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Biodiversity Human health Soil Waste Water 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Marine Strategy Framework Directive 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Nitrogen Phosphorus 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Pesticides Plastic, rubber and resins Pharmaceuticals Soil remediation Water and effluent treatment 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Chemical industry Food production industry Pharmaceutical industry Production of plastic and rubber 	
	Integrated Nutrient Management Action Plan	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Air Biodiversity Climate Marine Soil Waste Water 		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Nitrogen Phosphorus 	▼		▼
	Revision of the Sustainable Use of Pesticides Directive and enhance Integrated Pest Management provisions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Biodiversity Soil 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Sustainable Use of Pesticides Directive 		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Pesticides 		
Chemicals Strategy for Sustainability (28)	Develop methodologies for chemical risk assessment that take into account the whole life cycle of substances, materials and products		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Sustainable Product Policy Initiative 		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Electronics Paper and packaging Plastic, rubber and resins Stone, concrete and tile Textile and upholstery 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Chemical industry Electronic industry Production of plastic and rubber Textile production 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Circular Economy/Chemical content of (recycled) products
	Establishment of an open platform on chemical safety data and tools for accessing relevant academic data					<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Chemical industry 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Science-Policy Interface, research and monitoring
	Establish and update a research and innovation agenda for chemicals, driven by an EU-level Coordination Group, that would also promote the regulatory uptake of research findings						<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Science-Policy Interface, research and monitoring
	Foster multidisciplinary research and digital innovations for advanced tools, methods and models, and data analysis capacities to also move away from animal testing						<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Science-Policy Interface, research and monitoring

EU-Strategy:	Action/Measure:	Aims at	Legislation	Substance Groups/substances	Use	Sectors/industrial branches	General scope	
	Establish an EU Chemical Early Warning and Action System						<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Science-Policy Interface, research and monitoring 	
	Promote the development of common standards and innovative risk assessment tools internationally, notably with the OECD, and promote their use under international frameworks, inter alia to shift further away from animal testing.						<ul style="list-style-type: none"> International action 	
	Develop EU safe and sustainable-by-design criteria for chemicals		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> REACH Ecolabel Regulation Ecodesign Directive Industrial Emissions Directive 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Substances hampering recycling Substances included in the Candidate List under REACH Substances included in annex VI under the CLP regulation 			<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Circular Economy/Chemical content of (recycled) products Substitution of chemicals 	
	Establish Key Performance Indicators to measure the industrial transition towards the production of safe and sustainable chemicals.		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> REACH Ecolabel Regulation Ecodesign Directive Industrial Emissions Directive 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Substances hampering recycling Substances included in the Candidate List under REACH Substances included in annex VI under the CLP regulation 			<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Substitution of chemicals 	
	Roadmap to prioritise carcinogenic, mutagenic and reprotoxic substances (CMRs), endocrine disruptors, persistent, bioaccumulative and toxic (PBT and very persistent and very bioaccumulative (vPvB) substances, immunotoxicants, neurotoxicants, substances toxic to specific organs and respiratory sensitisers for (group) restrictions under REACH	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Consumers Human health Vulnerable Groups Workers 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> REACH 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> CMRs Endocrine disruptors PBT/vPvB substances Immunotoxicants & Neurotoxicants Substances toxic to specific organs Respiratory Sensitisers 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Childcare articles & toys Cleaning compositions Paper and packaging Personal care products Textile and upholstery 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Cosmetics Textile production 		
	Define criteria for essential uses, taking into account the definition of the Montreal Protocol, to ensure that the most harmful chemicals are only allowed if their use is necessary for health, safety or is critical for		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Montreal Protocol 					

EU-Strategy:	Action/Measure:	Aims at	Legislation	Substance Groups/substances	Use	Sectors/industrial branches	General scope
	the functioning of society and if there are no alternatives that are acceptable from the standpoint of environment and health. These criteria will guide the application of essential uses in all relevant EU legislation for both generic and specific risk assessments						
	<p>Establishment of a 'One substance, one assessment' process to coordinate the hazard/risk assessment on chemicals across chemical legislation, through the use of a single Public Authorities Coordination Tool, an expert group and a Commission coordination mechanism. Will be implemented through three legal proposals:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The reattribution of tasks on chemicals to EU Agencies (2022), - Transparency and reuse of data allowing EU and national authorities to commission testing (2023), and - ECHA's founding regulation (2023), to improve the predictability and stability of ECHA's financing <p>And through the development of a common open data portal on chemicals (2023) and a repository of health-based limit values.</p>		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • ECHA founding regulation • Public Activities Coordination Tool • REACH • CLP 				<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Regulatory harmonisation • Substance grouping
	Make amendments to the EU legislation on industrial emissions to promote the use of safer chemicals by EU industry (revision of the IED).		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Industrial Emissions Directive 				<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Substitution of chemicals
	Introduce legal requirements to minimise the presence of substances of concern in products, including PFAS, through the initiative on sustainable products, giving priority to those product categories that affect vulnerable populations as well as those with the highest potential for circularity, such as textiles, packaging including food packaging, furniture, electronics and ICT, construction and buildings	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Vulnerable groups 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Ecodesign Directive • Sustainable products initiative 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • PFAS 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Electronic devices • Paper and packaging • Stone, concrete and tile • Textile and upholstery 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Building and construction • Chemical industry • Electronic industry • Textile production 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Circular Economy/Chemical content of (recycled) products
	Ensure availability of information on chemical content and safe use, by introducing information requirements in the context of the Sustainable Product Policy Initiative and tracking the presence of substances of concern through the life cycle of materials and products		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Sustainable products initiative • REACH 		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Electronic devices • Stone, concrete and tile • Textile and upholstery 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Building and construction • Chemical industry • Electronic industry • Textile production 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Circular Economy/Chemical content of (recycled) products
	Proposals to extend the generic approach to risk management to ensure that consumer products (including, among other things, food contact materials, toys, childcare articles, cosmetics, detergents, furniture and textiles) do not contain chemicals that cause cancers, gene mutations, affect the reproductive or the endocrine system, or are persistent and bioaccumulative and toxic; assess through an impact assessment the modalities and timing to extend the same approach to further chemicals including those affecting the immune, neurological or respiratory systems and chemicals toxic to a specific organ	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Consumers 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Cosmetics Regulation • Detergents Regulation • Food Contact Materials Regulation • Toy Safety Directive 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • CMRs • Endocrine disruptors • PBT/vPvB substances • Immunotoxicants & Neurotoxicants • Substances toxic to specific organs 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Childcare articles & toys • Cleaning compositions • Paper and packaging • Personal care products 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Chemical industry • Cosmetics • Production of plastic and rubber • Textile production 	

EU-Strategy:	Action/Measure:	Aims at	Legislation	Substance Groups/substances	Use	Sectors/industrial branches	General scope
	Action implemented through the revisions of REACH, Cosmetics Regulation, Toy Safety Directive, Food Contact Materials Regulation, and other such as Detergents Regulation.		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> REACH 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Respiratory Sensitisers 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Textile and upholstery 		
	Introduce mandatory legal requirements under the General Product Safety Directive and restrictions in REACH to enhance the safety of children from hazardous chemicals in childcare articles and other products for children (other than toys)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Consumers Children 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> General Product Safety Directive REACH 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> CMRs Endocrine disruptors PBT/vPvB substances Immunotoxicants & Neurotoxicants Substances toxic to specific organs Respiratory Sensitisers 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Childcare articles & toys 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Production of plastic and rubber 	
	Assess how best and introduce (a) mixture assessment factor(s) in Annex I of REACH		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> REACH 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Mixtures 			
	Introduce or reinforce provisions to take account of the combination effects of chemicals in water, food contact materials, food additives, toys, detergents, cosmetics	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Water 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Environmental Quality Standards Directive Ground Water Directive Food contact materials regulation Food additives Commission Regulation Detergents Regulation Toy Safety Directive Cosmetic Products Regulation 		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Childcare articles & toys Cleaning compositions Food additives Paper and packaging Personal care products Water and effluent treatment 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Chemical industry Cosmetics Food production industry Production of plastic and rubber 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Combination effects of chemicals
	Proposal to amend the CLP Regulation to introduce new hazard classes on endocrine disruptors, PBTs/vPvBs and persistent and mobile substances, and apply them across all legislation		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> CLP 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Endocrine Disruptors PBT/vPvB PMT/vPvM 			
	Proposal to amend REACH Article 57 to add endocrine disruptors, persistent, mobile and toxic (PMT) and very persistent and very mobile (vPvM) substances to the list of substances of very high concern		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> REACH 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Endocrine Disruptors PMT/vPvM 			

EU-Strategy:	Action/Measure:	Aims at	Legislation	Substance Groups/substances	Use	Sectors/industrial branches	General scope
	Ensure that the information made available to authorities on substances allows comprehensive environmental risk assessments by strengthening requirements across legislation						
	Proposal to restrict PFAS as a group under REACH for all non-essential uses including in consumer products.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Consumers 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> REACH 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> PFAS 			<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Substance grouping
	<p>Address PFAS with a group approach, under relevant legislation on water, sustainable products, food, industrial emissions, and waste:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Review of the annexes of the Environmental Quality Standards Directive and of the Groundwater Directive to add PFAS where possible as a group Address the presence of PFAS in food by introducing limits in the legislation on food contaminants Proposal to revise the legislation on industrial emissions and the European Pollutant Release and Transfer Register to address emissions and reporting of PFAS from industrial plants Proposal to address the emissions of PFAS from the waste stage including through the revision of the legislation on sewage sludge 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Water Waste 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> European Pollutant Release and Transfer Register (E-PRTR) Environmental Quality Standards Directive Groundwater Directive Food Contaminants Commission Regulation Industrial Emissions Directive Sewage Sludge Directive 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> PFAS 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Water and effluent treatment 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Food production industry 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Substance grouping
	Proposals under the Stockholm Convention and the Basel Convention to address PFAS concerns at a global scale		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Basel Convention Stockholm Convention 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> PFAS 			<ul style="list-style-type: none"> International action
	Proposals to revise requirements for registration in REACH to ensure: the identification of substances with critical hazard properties, including effects on the nervous and immune systems, the move towards grouping approaches, the registration of a sub-set of polymers, information on the overall environmental footprint of chemicals, the obligation of chemical safety reports for substances between 1-10 tonnes		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> REACH 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Immunotoxicants & Neurotoxicants Polymers 		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Chemical industry 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Substance grouping
	Establish an EU-wide safe and sustainable-by design support network						<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Circular Economy/Chemical content of (recycled) products
	Financial support for the development, commercialisation, deployment and uptake of safe and sustainable-by-design substances, materials and products						<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Circular Economy/Chemical content of

EU-Strategy:	Action/Measure:	Aims at	Legislation	Substance Groups/substances	Use	Sectors/industrial branches	General scope	
							(recycled) products	
	Provide research and innovation funding for safe innovations to substitute PFAS under Horizon Europe			• PFAS			• Substitution of chemicals	
Circular Economy Action Plan (18)	Legislative proposal for a sustainable product policy initiative	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Climate Waste 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Ecodesign Directive Sustainable products initiative 		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Electronic devices Stone, concrete and tile Textile and upholstery 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Building and construction Chemical industry Electronic industry Textile production 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Circular Economy/Chemical content of (recycled) products 	
	Mandatory Green Public Procurement (GPP) criteria and targets in sectoral legislation and phasing-in mandatory reporting on GPP		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Sustainable products initiative 					
	Review of the Industrial Emissions Directive, including the integration of circular economy practices in upcoming Best Available Techniques (BAT) reference documents	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Climate 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Industrial Emissions Directive 					<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Circular Economy/Chemical content of (recycled) products
	Review of the Directive on the restriction of the use of certain hazardous substances in electrical and electronic equipment and guidance to clarify its links with REACH and Ecodesign requirements		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Directive on the restriction of the use of certain hazardous substances in electrical and electronic equipment Ecodesign Directive REACH 		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Electronic devices 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Chemical industry Electronic industry 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Circular Economy/Chemical content of (recycled) products 	
	Proposal for a new regulatory framework for batteries	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Climate 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Batteries Directive 		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Automotive Electronic devices 		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Circular Economy/Chemical content of (recycled) products 	
	Review of the rules on end-of-life vehicles	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Waste 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Directive on end-of-life vehicles 		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Automotive 		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Circular Economy/Chemical content of (recycled) products 	
	Review of the rules on proper treatment of waste oils	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Waste 			<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Automotive 		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Circular Economy/Chemical content of (recycled) products 	

EU-Strategy:	Action/Measure:	Aims at	Legislation	Substance Groups/substances	Use	Sectors/industrial branches	General scope
	Review to reinforce the essential requirements for packaging and reduce (over)packaging and packaging waste	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Waste Water 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Directive on packaging and packaging waste Drinking Water Directive 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Polymers 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Food contact materials Paper and packaging Plastic, rubber and resins 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Production of plastic and rubber 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Circular Economy/Chemical content of (recycled) products
	Mandatory requirements on recycled plastic content and plastic waste reduction measures for key products such as packaging, construction materials and vehicles	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Waste 			<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Automotive Paper and packaging Stone, concrete and tile 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Building and construction 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Circular Economy/Chemical content of (recycled) products
	Restriction of intentionally added microplastics and measures on unintentional release of microplastics	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Water 			<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Plastic, rubber and resins Textile and upholstery 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Production of plastic and rubber Textile production 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Circular Economy/Chemical content of (recycled) products
	Policy framework for bio-based plastics and biodegradable or compostable Plastics				<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Plastic, rubber and resins 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Production of plastic and rubber 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Circular Economy/Chemical content of (recycled) products
	EU Strategy for Textiles	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Waste 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> EU strategy for textiles 		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Textile and upholstery 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Chemical industry Textile production 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Circular Economy/Chemical content of (recycled) products
	Methodologies to track and minimize the presence of substances of concern in recycled materials and articles made thereof	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Human health Waste 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> REACH 				<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Circular Economy/Chemical content of (recycled) products Substitution of chemicals
	Harmonised information systems for the presence of substances of concern	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Waste 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> REACH Sustainable products initiative 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> SVHC 			<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Circular Economy/Chemical content of (recycled) products
	Revision of the rules on waste shipments	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Human health Waste 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Regulation on shipment of waste 				<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Circular Economy/Chemical content of (recycled) products

EU-Strategy:	Action/Measure:	Aims at	Legislation	Substance Groups/substances	Use	Sectors/industrial branches	General scope
	Reflecting circular economy objectives in the revision of the guidelines on state aid in the field of environmental and energy	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Waste 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> EU Taxonomy Regulation Guidelines on State aid for climate, environmental protection and energy 				<ul style="list-style-type: none"> International action Circular Economy/Chemical content of (recycled) products
	Leading efforts towards reaching a global agreement on plastics		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> European Plastic Strategy 		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Plastic, rubber and resins 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Production of plastic and rubber 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Circular Economy/Chemical content of (recycled) products International action
	Updating the Circular Economy Monitoring Framework to reflect new policy priorities and develop further indicators on resource use, including consumption and material footprints	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Climate 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Circular Economy Monitoring Framework 				<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Circular Economy/Chemical content of (recycled) products
Europe's Beating Cancer Plan (2)	Launch Horizon Europe Partnership on Assessment of Risks from Chemicals to strengthen EU capacities for chemical risk assessment	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Consumers Human health Workers 		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Carcinogenic Substances Endocrine disruptors Immunotoxicants 			<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Substitution of chemicals
	Reduce workers' exposure to carcinogenic substances through the amendments of the Carcinogens and Mutagens Directive	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Human health Workers 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Carcinogens and Mutagens Directive Occupational Safety and Health Strategic Framework 2021-2027 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Asbestos Acrylonitrile Benzene Carcinogenic Substances Nickel compounds 		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Chemical industry 	
Farm to Fork Strategy (2)	Proposal for a revision of the Sustainable Use of Pesticides Directive to significantly reduce use and risk and dependency on pesticides and enhance Integrated Pest Management	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Air Biodiversity Soil Water 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Sustainable Use of Pesticides Directive 		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Pesticides 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Chemical industry Food production industry 	
	Proposal for a revision of EU legislation on Food Contact Materials to improve food safety, ensure citizens' health and reduce the environmental footprint of the sector by Q4 2022	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Human health 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Food contact materials regulation 		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Food contact materials Paper and Packaging 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Chemical industry 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Circular Economy/Chemical content of (recycled) products

EU-Strategy:	Action/Measure:	Aims at	Legislation	Substance Groups/substances	Use	Sectors/industrial branches	General scope	
A New Industrial Strategy for Europe (6)	Promoting research and innovation through Horizon Europe (cluster 4 Digital, Industry and Space) on more sustainable alternatives to critical raw materials and chemicals – including better waste processing (recycling), innovative materials and increased substitution	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Waste 				<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Aerospace Chemical industry 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Circular Economy/Chemical content of (recycled) products Substitution of chemicals 	
	Periodic review of strategic dependencies and monitoring of risks associated with strategic dependencies					<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Energy sector 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> International action 	
	Development of EU principles on sustainable raw materials						<ul style="list-style-type: none"> International action 	
	Setting up of the Industrial Forum to support the implementation of the Strategy						<ul style="list-style-type: none"> International action 	
	Launch of industrial alliances for relevant industrial ecosystems, e.g. European Raw Materials Alliance					<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Electronic devices Plastic, rubber and resins 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Electronic industry Production of plastic and rubber 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> International action
	Co-creation of green and digital transition pathways for relevant ecosystems, starting with tourism and energy intensive industries			<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Batteries Regulation 			<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Building and Construction Chemical industry Energy Sector Manufacture of metal products 	
Pharmaceutical Strategy for Europe (1)	Propose to revise the pharmaceutical legislation to strengthen the environmental risk assessment requirements and conditions of use for medicines, and take stock of the results of research under the innovative medicines initiative	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Human health 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Directive on the Community code relating to medicinal products for human use Regulation laying down Union procedures for the authorization and supervision of medicinal products for human use and establishing a European Medicines Agency 			<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Pharmaceutical industry 		
A Renovation Wave for Europe	N/A							

EU-Strategy:	Action/Measure:	Aims at	Legislation	Substance Groups/substances	Use	Sectors/industrial branches	General scope
(0)							
EU Soil Strategy for 2030 (12)	Improve and harmonise the consideration of soil quality and soil biodiversity in EU risk assessments for chemicals, food and feed additives, pesticides, fertilizers, etc. It will do this under the 'one substance one assessment' initiative and in collaboration with the European Chemicals Agency (ECHA), the European Food Safety Authority (EFSA), the EEA, JRC and the Member States	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Biodiversity Soil 			<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Food contact materials Pharmaceuticals Pesticides Soil remediation 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Chemical industry Food production industry Pharmaceutical industry 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Regulatory harmonisation
	In cooperation with Member States and stakeholders, facilitate a dialogue and knowledge exchange on the risk assessment methodologies for soil contamination and identify best practices.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Soil 			<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Soil remediation 		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Stakeholder cooperation
	Work towards integrating a pollution module in the future LUCAS in 2022 soil survey to better understand and map the issue of diffuse soil contamination in the EU, and produce a clean soil outlook as part of the integrated zero pollution monitoring and outlook framework.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Soil 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Zero pollution monitoring and outlook framework 		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Soil remediation 		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Science-Policy Interface, research and monitoring
	Evaluate the Sewage Sludge Directive by 2022	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Soil 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Sewage Sludge Directive 				
	By 2023 evaluate the Environmental Liability Directive, including with regard to the definition of land damage and the role of financial security	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Soil 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Environmental Liability Directive 				
	By 2022, revise the Industrial Emissions Directive Revision ongoing. COM Proposal for a Directive adopted in April 2022.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Soil 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Industrial Emissions Directive 				
	Revise the Directive on the Sustainable Use of Pesticides by 2022	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Soil 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Sustainable Use of Pesticides Directive 		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Pesticides 		
	Restriction under REACH on all non-essential uses of the PFAS preventing their emission to the environment including soil Restriction dossier expected in January 2023.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Soil 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> REACH 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> PFAS 		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Chemical industry 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Substance grouping
	By 2024, develop an EU priority list for contaminants of major and/or emerging concern that pose significant risks for European soil quality, and for which vigilance and priority action at European and national level is needed.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Soil 			<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Soil remediation 		
	As part of the impact assessment for a Soil Health Law, the Commission will consider options for proposing legally binding provisions to i) identify contaminated sites, ii) set up an inventory and register of those sites and iii) remediate the sites that pose a significant risk to human health and the environment by 2050	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Soil 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Soil Health Law (Commission adoption July-October 2023) 		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Soil remediation 		
Through Horizon Europe and in particular the Mission 'A Soil Deal for Europe', the Commission will provide funding to research solutions to address soil degradation and pilot innovative technologies for decontamination	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Soil 			<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Soil remediation 			

EU-Strategy:	Action/Measure:	Aims at	Legislation	Substance Groups/substances	Use	Sectors/industrial branches	General scope
	Continue providing substantial funding to i) research solutions to increase soil biodiversity; ii) address soil degradation; iii) pilot innovative technologies for decontamination.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Biodiversity Soil 			<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Soil remediation 		
Sustainable Blue Economy Strategy (0)	N/A						
Sustainable Textile Strategy (15)	Mandatory performance requirements for the environmental sustainability of textile products under the new Ecodesign for Sustainable Products Regulation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Climate 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Ecodesign for Sustainable Products Regulation REACH 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> CMR substances 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Textile and upholstery 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Textile production 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Substitution of chemicals
	Digital Product Passport for textiles with information requirements on environmental sustainability under the new Ecodesign for Sustainable Products Regulation		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Ecodesign for Sustainable Products Regulation 		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Textile and upholstery 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Textile production 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Circular Economy/Chemical content of (recycled) products
	Mandatory requirements concerning green public procurement and Member State incentives under the new Ecodesign for Sustainable Products Regulation		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Ecodesign for Sustainable Products Regulation 		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Textile and upholstery 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Textile production 	
	Empowering consumers in the green transition and ensuring the reliability of green claims	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Consumers 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Directive as regards empowering consumers for the green transition through better protection against unfair practices and better information 		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Textile and upholstery 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Textile production 	
	Review of the Textile Labelling Regulation and considering the introduction of a digital label		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Textile Labelling Regulation 		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Textile and upholstery 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Textile production 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Circular Economy/Chemical content of (recycled) products
	Revision of the EU Ecolabel criteria for textiles and footwear		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Regulation on the EU Ecolabel 		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Textile and upholstery 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Textile production 	
	Initiative to address the unintentional release of microplastics from textile products	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Marine Waste Water 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Commission Initiative to address the unintentional 		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Cleaning compositions 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Chemical industry Machinery and equipment 	

EU-Strategy:	Action/Measure:	Aims at	Legislation	Substance Groups/substances	Use	Sectors/industrial branches	General scope
			<ul style="list-style-type: none"> release of microplastic into the environment • Ecodesign for Sustainable Products Regulation • Sewage Sludge Directive • Urban Waste Water Treatment Directive 		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Household applications • Textile and upholstery • Water and effluent treatment 	• Textile production	
	Review of the Best Available Techniques Reference Document for the Textiles Industry		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Best Available Techniques (BAT) Reference Document (BREF) • Industrial Emissions Directive 		• Textile and upholstery	• Textile production	
	Extended Producer Responsibility requirements for textiles with eco-modulation of fees and measures to promote the waste hierarchy for textile waste	• Waste	• Waste Framework Directive		• Textile and upholstery	• Textile production	• Circular Economy/Chemical content of (recycled) products
	Launch of work on the setting of preparing for re-use and recycling targets for textiles	• Waste	• Upcoming EU waste legislation in 2024		• Textile and upholstery	• Textile production	• Circular Economy/Chemical content of (recycled) products
	Launch of the Transition Pathway for the Textiles Ecosystem		• Ecodesign for Sustainable Products Regulation		• Textile and upholstery	• Textile production	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Circular Economy/Chemical content of (recycled) products • Stakeholder cooperation
	Launch of #ReFashionNow				• Textile and upholstery	• Textile production	• Circular Economy/Chemical content of (recycled) products
	Horizon Europe calls to support R&D in textiles				• Textile and upholstery	• Textile production	• Circular Economy/Chemical content of

EU-Strategy:	Action/Measure:	Aims at	Legislation	Substance Groups/substances	Use	Sectors/industrial branches	General scope
							(recycled) products
	Adoption of common industrial technology roadmap on circularity				• Textile and upholstery	• Textile production	• Circular Economy/Chemical content of (recycled) products
	Criteria for circular manufacturing of apparel under the Taxonomy Regulation		• Regulation on Taxonomy for Sustainable Investments		• Textile and upholstery	• Textile production	• Circular Economy/Chemical content of (recycled) products
Strategy for Plastics in a circular Economy (12)	Follow-up to COM (2018) 32 "Communication on the implementation of the circular economy package: options to address the interface between chemical, product and waste legislation": improve the traceability of chemicals and address the issue of legacy substances in recycled streams	• Waste	• Chemicals legislation • Product legislation • Waste legislation			• Chemical industry	• Circular Economy/Chemical content of (recycled) products
	As regards food-contact materials: swift finalization of pending authorization procedures for plastics recycling processes, better characterization of contaminants and introduction of monitoring system	• Waste			• Food contact materials • Plastic, rubber and resins	• Chemical industry • Production of plastic and rubber	• Circular Economy/Chemical content of (recycled) products
	Issue new guidelines on separate collection and sorting of waste	• Waste					• Circular Economy/Chemical content of (recycled) products
	Ensure better implementation of existing obligations on separate collection, including through ongoing review of waste legislation	• Waste					• Circular Economy/Chemical content of (recycled) products
	Adoption of a legislative proposal on port reception facilities for the delivery of waste from ships	• Marine • Waste	• Directive on port reception facilities for the delivery of waste from ships				• Circular Economy/Chemical content of (recycled) products
	Improved monitoring and mapping of marine litter, including microplastics, on the basis of EU harmonised methods	• Marine • Waste	• Best Available Techniques reference document for aquaculture installations			• Plastic, rubber and resins	• Production of plastic and rubber • Circular Economy/Chemical content of (recycled) products

EU-Strategy:	Action/Measure:	Aims at	Legislation	Substance Groups/substances	Use	Sectors/industrial branches	General scope
	Support to Member States on the implementation of their programs of measures on marine litter under the Marine Strategy Framework Directive, including the link with their waste/litter management plans under the Waste Framework Directive	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Marine Waste 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Marine Strategy Framework Directive 		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Plastic, rubber and resins 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Production of plastic and rubber 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Circular Economy/Chemical content of (recycled) products
	Commission guidance on the eco-modulation of EPR fees	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Waste 			<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Paper and packaging Plastic, rubber and resins 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Production of plastic and rubber 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Circular Economy/Chemical content of (recycled) products
	Pursue work on life-cycle impacts of alternative feedstocks for plastics production				<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Plastic, rubber and resins 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Production of plastic and rubber 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Circular Economy/Chemical content of (recycled) products
	Direct financial support for infrastructure and innovation through the European Fund for Strategic Investment and other EU funding instruments (e.g. structural funds and smart specialization strategies, Horizon 2020)						<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Circular Economy/Chemical content of (recycled) products
	Support to action under the Basel Convention, particularly for the implementation of the toolkit on environmentally sound waste management	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Waste 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Basel Convention Regulation on waste shipments 		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Plastic, rubber and resins 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Production of plastic and rubber 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Circular Economy/Chemical content of (recycled) products International action
	Preparatory work for future revision of the Packaging and Packaging Waste Directive: Commission to initiate work on new harmonised rules to ensure that by 2030 all plastics packaging placed on the EU market can be reused or recycled in a cost-effective manner.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Waste 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Packaging and Packaging Waste Directive Directive on End-of-Life Vehicles 		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Paper and packaging Plastic, rubber and resins 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Production of plastic and rubber 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Circular Economy/Chemical content of (recycled) products Regulatory harmonisation
Zero Pollution Action Plan (25)	Reducing health inequalities through zero pollution. Regularly feed pollution monitoring and outlook data into the Cancer Inequalities Registry and the Atlas of Demography's.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Human health 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Atlas of Demography Cancer Inequalities Registry 				
	Review and, if necessary, revise the Bathing Water Directive	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Water 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Bathing Water Directive 		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Water and effluent treatment 		
	Support the implementation of the new Drinking Water Directive and adopt relevant implementing and delegated acts	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Human health Water 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Drinking Water Directive 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Endocrine disruptors 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Plastic, rubber and resins 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Chemical industry Production of plastic and rubber 	

EU-Strategy:	Action/Measure:	Aims at	Legislation	Substance Groups/substances	Use	Sectors/industrial branches	General scope	
					<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Water and effluent treatment 			
	Promoting zero pollution across regions. In cooperation with the Committee of the Regions, present a Scoreboard of EU regions' green performance to measure, in particular, efforts to achieve pollution-relevant targets.							
	Review and, if necessary, revise the Marine Strategy Framework Directive	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Marine 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Marine Strategy Framework Directive 		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Plastic, rubber and resins 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Chemical industry Production of plastic and rubber 		
	Reduce underwater noise and marine litter through EU threshold values to be set under the Marine Strategy Framework Directive	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Marine 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Marine Strategy Framework Directive 		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Plastic, rubber and resins 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Building and construction Mining Oil & gas industry Production of plastic and rubber 		
	Revise the Urban Waste Water Treatment Directive in synergy with the review of the Industrial Emissions Directive and the evaluation of the Sewage Sludge Directive	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Human health Waste Water 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Urban Waste Water Treatment Directive Industrial Emissions Directive Sewage Sludge Directive 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Endocrine disruptors 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Pharmaceuticals Plastic, rubber and resins Water and effluent treatment 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Chemical industry Food production industry Pharmaceutical industry Production of plastic and rubber 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Circular Economy/Chemical content of (recycled) products 	
	Identify and remedy contaminated sites by investigating best practices and providing guidance for a passport for the safe, sustainable and circular use of excavated soil	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Human health Soil 				<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Soil remediation 		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Circular Economy/Chemical content of (recycled) products
	Identify and remedy contaminated sites by facilitating and promoting awareness of public and private funding for identification, investigation, assessment and remediation of contaminated soils and groundwater.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Human health Soil Water 				<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Soil remediation 		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Circular Economy/Chemical content of (recycled) products
	Revise the Environmental Quality Standards Directive and the Groundwater Directive	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Water 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Environmental Quality Standards Directive Groundwater Directive 					
	Support the implementation of the Strategic Guidelines for a more sustainable and competitive EU aquaculture - Environmental performance aspects	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Human health Water 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Strategic Guidelines for a more sustainable and competitive EU aquaculture 				<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Chemical industry Food production industry 	

EU-Strategy:	Action/Measure:	Aims at	Legislation	Substance Groups/substances	Use	Sectors/industrial branches	General scope
	Revision of the Industrial Emissions Directive and the E-PRTR Regulation		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> European Pollutant Release and Transfer Register (E-PRTR) Industrial Emissions Directive 				
	Facilitating zero pollution choices. Encourage public and private sector operators to make 'zero pollution pledges' to promote best available, 'nearzero-waste' and least polluting options.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Waste 					▼
	Revise the Environmental Crime Directive	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Human health 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Environmental Crime Directive 				
	Fitness check of the Environmental Liability Directive	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Human health 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Environmental Liability Directive 				
	Enforcing zero pollution together. Bring together environmental and other enforcement authorities to kick off the exchange of best practices and encourage Member States to devise cross sectorial compliance actions towards zero tolerance for pollution at national level and transboundary level.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Air Human health Soil Water 					
	Build capacity and improve knowledge on less polluting practices with national advisory services for farmers	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Soil 		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Ammonia Nitrate 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Soil remediation 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Food production industry 	
	Create a zero-pollution contribution to the European Green Deal Dataspace to improve data availability		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> A European Strategy for Data 				
	Support initiatives to better monitor and manage international trade for waste electrical and electronic equipment (WEEE) and waste batteries	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Waste 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Basel Convention Rotterdam Convention Stockholm Convention Minamata Convention 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Mercury Persistent organic pollutants (POP) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Automotive Electronic devices 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Chemicals industry Electronic industry 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Science-Policy Interface, research and monitoring
	Support global action on the export of end-of-life and used vehicles	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Waste 			<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Automotive 		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> International action
	Support a global initiative to end informal recycling of used lead acid batteries	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Waste 		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Lead 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Automotive Electronic devices 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Electronic industry 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Circular Economy/Chemical content of (recycled) products International action

EU-Strategy:	Action/Measure:	Aims at	Legislation	Substance Groups/substances	Use	Sectors/industrial branches	General scope
	Minimizing the EU's external pollution footprint. Promote global zero pollution in all relevant international fora and work with the EU Member States and stakeholders.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Waste 					<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • International action
	Zero Pollution Monitoring and Outlook Reports	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Human health • Soil 					<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Science-Policy Interface, research and monitoring • Stakeholder cooperation
	Develop a 'European Environment and Health Atlas'	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Human health • Soil 					
	Launch the Zero Pollution Stakeholder Platform (including thematic hubs, e.g. on digital solutions, clean air tech, soil pollution)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Climate • Human health • Soil 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • European Climate Pact 				<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Stakeholder cooperation
Total actions/measures: 124							

H2020 project Zero pollution of Persistent, Mobile substances
EU Grant Agreement No. 101036756